
Master Thesis

in

Information Science and Language Technology M.A.

Development and evaluation of a language level search engine

presented by

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Source Code

<https://github.com/elaisasearch/elaisa.org>

Productive Environment

<https://elaisa.org/>

Abstract

Nowadays, many different search engines are available with which almost all documents on the Internet can be found. However, if one wants to find articles based on the respective language level of the texts they contain, none of the search engines that can be used provide such a functionality. For this reason, this master thesis is concerned with the development of a language-based search engine, with which results can be found based on the chosen language, language level, and a search term. The ultimate goal was to find out how to create such a search engine that focuses on the categorization of text documents. In addition, an evaluation should be carried out to determine whether the final application returns sufficient results. Therefore, three tests were carried out and their results analyzed, in which one of them concentrated on the usability of the user interface to improve it in the course of development.

*I dedicate this thesis to my parents
Gabriele and Winfried Teusz*

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CEFR	Common European Framework of Reference for Languages
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSS	Cascading Style Scheets
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTML	Hyptertext Markup Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
ID	Identifier
IDF	Inverse Document Frequency
IR	Information Retrieval
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KISS	Keep It Simple, Stupid
MVC	Model/View/Controller
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NLU	Natural Language Understanding
REST	Representational State Transfer
SMART	System for the Mechanical Analysis and Retrieval of Text
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
UI	User Interface
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WWW	World Wide Web
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1 Introduction

”People keep asking me what I think of it now it’s done. Hence my protest: The Web is not done!”

Tim Berners-Lee (Wired, 1999)

As the inventor of the World Wide Web (WWW) Mr. Tim Berners-Lee said in an interview with Wired Magazine in 1999, his project is not done yet. He already knew that there would be thousands of different services using the basic infrastructure of a global network and demand a further development. Twenty years later, almost everyone with the possibility to go online uses Berners-Lee’s invention. Clement (2019) mentions that there was an estimated 3.9 billion Internet users worldwide in 2017. Due to this, search engines such as Google¹ nowadays have to be able to “index many billions of web pages [...]” (Levene, 2011, p. 1) or other sorts of media like videos or images. Even though it may look like Google or Yahoo² first dealt with this topic, their actual roots lie in the technology of Information Retrieval (IR) which can be traced back to the late 1950s when Luhn published his work about the automatic creation of literature abstracts (1958). From this time forward, various scientists such as Gerard Salton (1988) researched and developed new techniques to make documents traceable. Not least, the development of the System for the Mechanical Analysis and Retrieval of Text (SMART) played a major role in this period since many important concepts of IR were developed as part of research on this system; published at Cornell University in the 1960s (Salton & McGill, 1983). As computers got more powerful and accordingly more opportunities arose to work with large amounts of data, it was only a matter of time until scientists and software engineers would create the first globally accessible search engine. In February 1994, Yahoo was released as one of the earliest worldwide search services, at which point it was “only providing a browsable directory, organizing web pages into categories which were classified by human editors” (Levene, 2011, p. 7-8). In the following years various search engines were published and built up new possibilities for private users to access thousands of different websites with a click of a button. Today it can be said that almost all human knowledge is stored in approximately 6.08 billion indexed documents which can be found with a specific search (de Kunder, 2019).

1.1 Variations of Search Engines

When talking about the histories of these companies, it may seem like there are no unresolved tasks anymore regarding the retrieval of information. However, the Internet provides us with many different variants, such as web crawler search engines (Google, Bing), meta search engines (Ecosia,

¹<https://www.google.com/>

²<https://de.yahoo.com/>

DuckDuckGo, WolframAlpha) or target-group search engines (Kiddle) (Seymour, Frantsvog, & Kumar, 2011). Yahoo's first version, for example, was a catalog-based (web directory) search engine because each document was classified by a human. Some examples should be looked at more closely (2011):

*Kiddle*³, for example, aims to develop a search engine for child-friendly usage. It prevents inappropriate content and prepares the search results in a way that is in turn appropriate for children, so that they can concentrate on the essentials. For this reason, a few responses also refer to websites that are marked with 'for kids'. In conclusion, such a variant is very helpful for children, since their search behavior differs from adults. Children are more likely to look for main topics, although adults often have a certain website in mind that could provide an answer (Gossen, Low, & Nürnberger, 2011).

In addition to focusing on target-group-specific searches, *Ecosia*⁴ aims for a contribution to environmental protection with every search. There, it "does not run an own search index because of financial and technological restrictions" (Schmidt, Ruch, Decker, & Kolbe, 2012, p. 6) but uses Bing and Yahoo to display search results and sponsored links to the user. Up to 80% percent of the revenues are sponsored to WWF⁵ for rainforest protection programs. With this business model Ecosia was able to generate over 11,000 EUR of revenues with around nine million search requests in April 2010 (2012).

If one includes the personal data of a person in this overview, *DuckDuckGo*⁶ wants to maintain privacy and thus prevent the sale of private data to third parties. On their website it says, they are the "Search Engine, that doesn't track you" (DuckDuckGo, 2020) in which none of the searches are stored. This in turn means, that there is no personalized advertising as well.

Another meta search engine is *WolframAlpha*⁷ that tries to prepare results as best as possible for the user. It is recognized whether the user wants so calculate something or needs detailed information about a topic. Regarding the preparation, the results view changes. Based on *Mathematica*⁸, WolframAlpha uses computational intelligence to answer almost every questions a user could have.

If one now takes a step further into the areas of scientific approaches, *Scopus*⁹ and *WebofScience*¹⁰ can be used as examples. Both are used to search for scientific articles for papers or other sorts of research. On the one hand, they provide a full-text search to get an overview about articles that concentrate on the wanted topic. On the other hand, the user can search for keywords, authors or topics to filter a possible long list of results. In order to get the best result for the user's need of information, both include an *advanced search* feature, where one can type in a query string. This query though consists of field tags and boolean operators, for example.

³<https://www.kiddle.co/>

⁴<https://www.ecosia.org/>

⁵<https://www.wwf.de/>

⁶<https://duckduckgo.com/>

⁷<https://www.wolframalpha.com/>

⁸<https://www.wolfram.com/mathematica/>

⁹<https://www.scopus.com/search/form.uri?display=basic>

¹⁰<https://apps.webofknowledge.com/>

Now these examples have already been published and are available to the community. With the constant renewal of the technologies, however, new approaches in research are sought to provide the search for all kinds of information. This is how completely new thoughts come to light, such as emotional indexing and emotional retrieval of multimedia documents (Siebenlist, 2012).

1.2 Idea

If one now takes these considerations to think about not yet available search engines, it can be found that no engine with the discovery of different text documents (websites, articles, etc.) with a certain language level is developed. This means that it is not yet possible to search for documents based on their language level. The following example can be used as an explanation: If a student wants to improve her pronunciation and vocabulary for Spanish lessons, it usually helps to read texts that the teacher has classified as suitable. Often, however, one finds rather obsolete or fictional texts in textbooks that have no exact reference to current events. Furthermore, current news would be a better source, since in lessons or in other conversations these topics can be understood directly and may be more interesting than typical texts from a book. If the student can improve her vocabulary, or better said language skills, by reading interesting news articles from time to time, she will be able to search for articles in a more difficult language level until she is able to speak Spanish fluently at some point. It is precisely from such an example that the idea arose to concentrate completely on the needs of a student learner.

Besides Spanish, the same person could also choose German or English as result language to learn. These three choices were made, since English and Spanish are listed in the **Top 10 Languages By Number Of Native Speakers**¹¹. German, however, is included as it is spoken natively by the thesis' author. Regarding the project's name, it can be said that it is created based on three keywords that came up in this thesis: *language*, *language level*, and *search engine*. Summarized as an abbreviation, they result in *LLSE*. To make it easier to say, the web application's name is *Elaisa*. The thesis will use this name in the course of the chapters to describe the search engine's final stage.

1.3 Goals

The aim of this work is therefore to develop a working search engine that can be used online by all interested users. In doing so, it should permanently provide up-to-date articles and satisfy the user experience by providing the option to learn a language at a high level. In terms of the various devices, the web application must be able to be easily used on a computer or mobile phone (Pooker, 2011, p. 547; Reiss, 2015, p. 55-57). Accordingly, a global user-friendly design must be used that places the core functions on any device in the foreground (Obilade, 2020, p. 14). Furthermore, the search itself must not take a long time; results must be displayed as soon as possible. The best case would

¹¹<https://www.babbel.com/en/magazine/the-10-most-spoken-languages-in-the-world>

be to provide an instant search (Cetindil, Esmaelnezhad, Li, & Newman, 2012, p. 1). As additional functions, Wikipedia articles can be displayed on search terms and a user profile can be created to observe the search history and the resulting progress.

Based on the above, the following research questions arise:

- How can a modern and scalable search engine be developed that provides to find documents that are categorized by language level?
- How can documents be categorized and searched based on language level?

1.4 Overview

In order to get an overview about how this work will answers these questions, section 2 will concentrate on how to develop a search engine in theory. Section 3 will then focus on helpful technologies such as programming languages and a suitable architecture for all needed services. Furthermore, it will explain the used methods and search application's logic based on Information Retrieval theories and techniques to build a functioning backend system.

1.4.1 Evaluation

Section 3 will end with the presentation of three evaluations which are used to improve the final application regarding testers' suggestions, for example. These are inevitable, as a random user must be able to find result documents. These results must correspond to the need of information and at the same time have been correctly categorized. This means whether a result, which according to Elaisa contains a text in language level C1, can really be classified as C1.

1.4.2 Results and Discussion

After that, part 4 will present the analysis of the test results and also show the developed application. It will also show how to use the final search engine on desktop and mobile devices. Finally, a discussion (see section 5) will deal with future tasks, limitations, and further ways of creating a modern search engine since this work only demonstrates one of several approaches. Additionally, possible improvements will be addressed.

2 Theory: Information Retrieval

Before describing which methods this thesis uses to answer the research questions, the theoretical foundation of the developed search engine will be explained in general. Thus, the following section focuses on web crawlers, ranking procedures, and inverted indexes.

2.1 Web Crawler

The main part of every search engine is its web crawler. The web crawler's task is to crawl the WWW and extract the needed data from a currently analyzed web page. Generally, the basic algorithm starts from a so-called seed list, containing Uniform Resource Locators (URLs) to visit first. The more URLs are stored in this list, the wider the crawler can find necessary data (Pant, Srinivasan, & Menczer, 2004). Figure 1 visually shows what the basic process looks like, in a nutshell. After a

Figure 1: Basic crawler algorithm

Source: (Levene, 2011, p. 82)

URL is taken from the seed list, the connected web page will be visited and indexed. Once the crawler indexed the page, meaning extracting the informative content, the used and all found URLs on the website are added to the seed list. Figure 2 shows an overview of how the crawler is able to follow all links on a page.

Adding all URLs shall prevent crawling duplicates and expand the basis, but beside duplicates, there are some other problems web crawlers have to resolve. Talking about the list of seeds, it is very important to discuss which URLs should be inserted into it. The website behind the URL has to show good quality since “a crawler will have problems indexing a page that has errors such as misspecified

URLs” (Levene, 2011, p. 83). Also modern web applications, like the one developed in this work, often use dynamic Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) where scripts not only modify the look of a page, but also the content. This means a “crawler will find [...] [them] hard to interpret and therefore, may ignore them” (Levene, 2011, p. 83).

Figure 2: Crawling the Web. The web crawler connects to web servers to find pages. Pages may link to other pages on the same server or on different servers.

Source: (Croft, Metzler, & Strohman, 2010, p. 34)

2.2 Ranking

A user for example searches for articles about 'Germany' or 'Donald Trump' but only wants to read the results that best match the search request; the results have to be arranged according to a specific procedure. This is not only interesting with regards to this work, as Ramos from the Rutgers University states:

“The task of retrieving data from a user-defined query has become so common and natural in recent years that some might not give it a second thought. However, this growing use of query retrieval warrants continued research and enhancements to generate better solutions to the problem.” (Ramos et al., 2003, p. 1)

To solve this problem, a search engine can make use of the following two ranking methods: Term Frequency and PageRank. In this case, the retrieval models are Text Statistics and Link Typology (Stock

& Stock, 2013, p. 148-152). The first one uses the frequency of occurrence for a word in a document, more precisely the *TF/IDF* formula (Ramos et al., 2003). The more often a word appears in a result document the more important may it be for the user as it is part of the search query. Documents with a high term frequency for the given words may talk about the topic a user searches for. That alone wouldn't pay attention on the Inverse Document Frequency (IDF), that says how significant a term is in total. It represents the second part of the used *TF/IDF* formula (Stock & Stock, 2013, p. 278-286). For an easier understanding of the text statistical method of calculating the term frequency the following example is given:

A document contains overall 1000 words; the word 'summer' appears 68 times. The entire corpus consists of 10,000 documents and 2,000 of them contain the term 'summer'. The term frequency is now calculated as

$$TF = \frac{freq(word)}{sum(wordsInDocument)}$$

$$TF = \frac{68}{1000}$$

$$TF = 0.068$$

and IDF as the following using all documents containing the term for calculating the logarithm:

$$IDF = \log\left(\frac{sum(allDocuments)}{sum(documentsContainingTerm)}\right)$$

$$IDF = \log\left(\frac{10000}{2000}\right)$$

$$IDF = 1.212$$

Multiplying both results returns the *TF/IDF* value used as one part of the search engine's ranking process:

$$W_{t,d} = TF(t,d) \times IDF(t)$$

where $TF(t,d)$ is the number of occurrences of t in document d and $IDF(t)$ the number of documents containing the term t (Stock & Stock, 2013, p. 284-285).

Although the system now knows which documents may be interesting regarding the given term, it doesn't know if the currently best-rated website is also well connected to other sites on the WWW. Let's use the previous example and imagine the user gets a document talking exactly about the searched topic but doesn't include any links to other sites. The user is stuck in this one page and isn't able to navigate to resources this page used or any other interesting articles connected to the current one. As a solution, a value has to be calculated that shows how well a website is connected to show if it is probable that a user would navigate to this site if he or she randomly clicks links.

This 'user clicks random links' technique is used by Google's PageRank algorithm, as it "reflects the chance of the surfer arriving at the page" (Levene, 2011, p. 112). The inventors Brin and Page explain their algorithm as the following:

"PageRank can be thought of as a model of user behavior. We assume there is a 'random surfer' who is given a Web page at random and keeps, clicking on links, never hitting 'back' but eventually gets bored and starts on another random page." (Brin & Page, 1998, p. 110)

Figure 3 illustrates how such a random surfer could proceed navigating. Starting from document *B*,

Figure 3: Example web site to illustrate PageRank
Source: (Levene, 2011, p. 113)

the probability of clicking any of the outgoing link is $1/n$; in this case 0.25 ($1/4$). For all pages except for *A* there is at least one outgoing link. If the user visits *A* he or she is stuck in a dead end and has to restart the search; the problem that was mentioned before in the upper part of this section. To automatically start a new search PageRank uses teleportation to let the user begin from another random page on the web. Thus, the user never stops his travel (Levene, 2011, p. 112). However, the random user is also occasionally allowed to teleport himself or herself to any page whenever he or she wants, to simulate the state of getting bored of the current page (Page, Brin, Motwani, & Winograd,

1999). This probability is represented as T with a default value of 0.15 (Brin & Page, 1998). If one now packs everything theoretical together into one function, the PageRank looks like this, where a is the example web page:

- $L(a)$ is the set of websites that link to a
- $C(b)$ is the out-degree of page b
- T is the probability of random jump
- N is the total number of websites

$$PR(x) = T \left(\frac{1}{N} \right) + (1 - T) \sum_{y \in L(x)} \frac{PR(y)}{C(y)}$$

2.3 Inverted Index

Besides crawling documents and list them by a calculated rank, they have to be searchable as well. Meant is the capability of a fast search, provided by implementing an inverted index:

“The purpose of the Indexer is to decompose and prepare the documents supplied by the crawler so that they can be efficiently processed in the search.” (Lewandowski, 2018, p. 48)

Why this technique is so important can be shown with the following example: Imagine the document database is filled with 1,000,000 crawled websites and the user wants to search for the term ‘football’. From scratch, the system doesn’t know which documents contain this search value; it has to go through the entire database and parse the stored texts and try to find the needed ones. This may take a lot of unnecessary time. Even if there is no document containing the term ‘football’, the user still has to wait until the system is finished parsing the database. Nowadays, this problem is no longer significant as modern search engines are all based on *inverted indexes*. Such an index is “the computational equivalent of the index found in the back of [...] [a] textbook” (Croft et al., 2010, p. 132). If one wants to read something about a specific term that might be described in a book, one searches for it in the index and leaf to the listed sides. Exactly this procedure is used as basic idea in search engines. There, it is called *inverted* since it isn’t thought of as words as being part of documents, but documents associated with words. Figure 4 from (Croft et al., 2010, p. 136) can be considered to see how an exemplary inverted index looks that could be used in this work. As can be seen, each entry is composed of the term and a list of number-pairs where each pair represents the frequency of the term in a document. Therefore, the word ‘and’ appears one time in the first document. Unnecessary to say that this technique speeds up the search process a lot because the system now only has to find the searched term in the database and return all documents that are listed next to it. Thus, it is also easy to combine several terms with query Boolean such as *OR* and *AND*.

and	1:1				only	2:1
aquarium	3:1				pigmented	4:1
are	3:1	4:1			popular	3:1
around	1:1				refer	2:1
as	2:1				referred	2:1
both	1:1				requiring	2:1
bright	3:1				salt	1:1 4:1
coloration	3:1	4:1			saltwater	2:1
derives	4:1				species	1:1
due	3:1				term	2:1
environments	1:1				the	1:1 2:1
fish	1:2	2:3	3:2	4:2	their	3:1
fishkeepers	2:1				this	4:1
found	1:1				those	2:1
fresh	2:1				to	2:2 3:1
freshwater	1:1	4:1			tropical	1:2 2:2 3:1
from	4:1				typically	4:1
generally	4:1				use	2:1
in	1:1	4:1			water	1:1 2:1 4:1
include	1:1				while	4:1
including	1:1				with	2:1
iridescence	4:1				world	1:1
marine	2:1					
often	2:1	3:1				

Figure 4: An inverted index, with word counts [...]

Source: (Croft et al., 2010, p. 136)

3 Methods: Development of the Search Engine

At the beginning of this project, which arose from a seminar work that dealt with the practical development of a search engine, thinking about key features this search engine should offer was the first important step to take.

- What should the user search for?
- What are the search features?
- How should these features be implemented?

In general, the most basic feature a search engine could offer is the functionality of finding things, such as websites. Therefore, there should be some form of storage, since there is a need for a database containing crawled documents to make them available throughout the application. The user should be able to visit the search engine's website, type in a query including the term, language level, and result language and finally click on a website presented in the list of results. This requires providing enhancements to the usability factor of the application, for instance by using a user-friendly design. As one dives deeper into thinking about key features, it becomes clear that most, if not all of them revolve around how to provide the best possible search to the user – the main task and goal of every IR system. However, this project is not supposed to be a copy of Google, one last problem to think about is the main difference to others – the calculation and presentation of the language level of a particular document, in this case websites. Since the user, for example could search for English websites with the topic 'Donald Trump' and a certain language level, first the database needs to store each website's language analysis containing all required information. Secondly, the results page needs to show an overview of the calculated analysis to let the user decide which of the shown results he or she wants to read. In order to make use of the advantages modern web browsers offer, this overview should be displayed as a Graphical User Interface (GUI). Ultimately, all the services used must be able to work together with ease.

Overall the development of the application revolved around five main parts:

- Planning and developing the website
- Defining the algorithm to calculate a website's language level
- Developing a web crawler for gathering data shown as results
- Using common IR techniques to search for documents
- Hosting the entire application on a server to make it accessible on the Internet

3.1 Common European Framework of Reference for Languages

Starting with the idea of categorizing documents by language level, any basis needs to be implemented that offers the functionality to calculate if a document is written in easy or advanced English, for example.

The application uses the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) to let the user choose his or her actual state of knowledge regarding the chosen result language – like the mentioned example in the upper section. In a nutshell, CEFR is a “transparent, coherent and comprehensive reference instrument” developed by the Council of Europe over the last twenty years to be a basis for curriculum guidelines, teaching and learning materials (Council of Europe, 2019). Meanwhile, theorists, researchers, and language professionals tried to “describe what it means to learn languages and how they could be operationalized [...] for assessment purposes” (Figueras, 2012, p. 477).

To distinguish one student’s current learning status from another, this framework uses so-called language levels, which are divided into three broad categories: A, B, and C. Overall there are six main levels, described in “general terms and in relation to language activities and language tasks in over 50 descriptor scales, commonly referred to as the ‘vertical dimension’” (Figueras, 2012, p. 477) such as shown in Figure 5. Using the vocabulary assigned to the individual levels, a categorizer can calculate

Figure 5: CEFR: The vertical dimension
Source: Modified from (Figueras, 2012, p. 477)

for each document whether it is written in A2 or B1, for example. Since this has to be done for every document, it can be built into the web crawler’s workflow. Based on the calculated results, a user can ultimately filter his or her search based on the language level.

3.2 Third-Party Software

While developing the search engine, a few popular third-party software packages and frameworks were used to ease the development process from start to finish, since they provide various features to easily create functional and user-friendly web applications. Besides Docker, all of them were chosen before the actual programming process, as they are free to use and work together very well. It would be beyond the scope of the thesis to present and describe each of these libraries in detail, which is why the following sections will give a basic overview of what they were built for.

3.2.1 React

*React*¹² is a Javascript library for building and designing User Interfaces (UIs), which performs data viewing with the help of the HTML. Next to other popular Javascript UI technologies, such as *AngularJS*¹³ or *Vue.js*¹⁴, Facebook's competitor is rather new on the market. In the year 2011 the software engineer Jordan Walke created the first version, later it was used in Facebook's newsfeed and for developing Instagram's front-end system (Education Ecosystem, 2019). As time went by and the library grew up to a powerful tool, the company decided to open up the project for other developers in 2013. Now the GitHub repository¹⁵ counts more than 130,000 stars and is used by more than 2,3 million people around the world. With regard to the further development of the search engine using an Open-Source community, JavaScript in conjunction with React and Node.JS¹⁶ offers all the prerequisites for long-term maintenance (Springer, 2013, p. 23).

The main concept is to render so-called components into a single-page-application, which means that there is only one HTML file – the required **index.html**. Every time the user routes to another page the browser won't reload the whole page but change the required components to present the new view. By that, one of the biggest advantages of the concept of components is the very simple and fast maintenance of the code, since the developer, for example, defines a button in the code once and can use it again wherever he or she wants. Small code changes can effect the whole life cycle of a React application. Therefore, the "client scripts [...] makes sure that only necessary and essential data is pushed, and a seamless and pleasing experience is maintained across the entire web" (Aggarwal, 2018, p. 136).

All in all, there are a few more features React provides, which are also included in the search engine' code, but too complex to be described in an overview.

3.2.2 Material-UI

Having a clear component-based code structure represents the basis of the search engine's front-end, but when it comes to design there has to be a provided software solution which takes away the conceptual design of user-friendly and nice looking interfaces. For modern web applications the Open-Source library *Material-UI*¹⁷ is one major candidate, whereby it is used to design the web view in this thesis. Due to the already mentioned popularity of React, there is a free to use collection of React component examples on the Internet. This means, the developer doesn't have to build the components from scratch, he or she can use the example code and match it to the rest. In the end, it takes

¹²<https://reactjs.org/>

¹³<https://angularjs.org/>

¹⁴<https://vuejs.org/>

¹⁵<https://github.com/facebook/react>

¹⁶<https://nodejs.org/en/>

¹⁷<https://material-ui.com/>

almost no time to develop a persistently usable user experience so that time resources can be used for the functionality of the web application. An additional benefit is that Material-UI matches the design of Google’s well known web applications, such as Google Search and YouTube. This is due to the design philosophy that the company uses in all its products – Material Design¹⁸. On the website it says, that “Material is an adaptable system of guidelines, components, and tools that support the best practices of user interface design. Backed by Open-Source code, Material streamlines collaboration between designers and developers, and helps teams quickly build beautiful products.” (Google, 2020).

Based on Google’s public profile, the user should be familiar with all parts of the website and gets along quickly.

3.2.3 Bottle

As the developers describe *Bottle* on their own website¹⁹, “Bottle is a fast, simple, and lightweight WSGI micro web framework for Python” (Bottle, 2019). Besides other Python web frameworks like *Flask*²⁰ and *Django*²¹, this one should be the right choice for small and defined tasks.

This does not mean that Bottle does not provide the functionality to develop a full working web application. However, this thesis uses only a small part of the functions, namely the development of an Application Programming Interface (API). Such an interface should be designed in a clear and structured way so that it can seamlessly connect all services required. Thus, Bottle’s only task is to route the users request to the responsible handlers and return the found results.

Moreover, the effort to create a working program is much lower than with other frameworks, since the only required configuration fits into five lines of code:

```
1 from bottle import route, run, template
2
3 @route('/hello/<name>')
4 def index(name):
5     return template('<b>Hello {{name}}</b>!', name=name)
6
7 run(host='localhost', port=8080)
```

Code Listing 1: Python Bottle 'Hello World' Example

¹⁸<https://material.io/>

¹⁹<https://bottlepy.org/docs/dev/>

²⁰<https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/1.0.x/>

²¹<https://www.djangoproject.com/>

3.2.4 Scrapy

When it comes to the question how a search engine works, so-called web crawlers play an important role. A more elaborate description of this technology, will be described in section 3.3.2.

*Scrapy*²² is “an Open-Source and collaborative [Python] framework for extracting the data you need from websites.”, as is described on the framework’s web page (Scrapy, 2020). It is used in several projects from different companies to scrape the web (Rahmatullin, 2020). Moreover, on the website it says: “[...] In a fast, simple, yet extensible way” (Scrapy, 2020). Indeed, it is possible to get all necessary information from a website by defining a so-called spider. The spider’s job is to crawl through certain websites and pick the required data out of it. Afterwards it organizes everything and stores it into any form of a data storage – in this case MongoDB database (see section 3.2.5) to make it accessible to the entire application. For this reason, beside other Open-Source crawlers such as *Apache Nutch*²³, *Bixo*²⁴, *Heritrix*²⁵ and *Crawler4j*²⁶, Scrapy is a good choice, as it provides tools for crawling and scraping (Matsudaira, 2014, p. 10-11).

A web crawler has to continuously run to keep the database up to date, since the main task is to provide the latest information, which is published as articles on the Internet. The crawler service should therefore be as light as possible, and Scrapy is a good fit for this purpose. In fact, as with Bottle, this Python framework doesn’t require a lot of code to set up; a spider is defined as a Python class whose only method, called *parse()*, contains the entire logic.

```
class BlogSpider(scrapy.Spider):
2     name = 'blogspider'
      start_urls = ['https://blog.scrapinghub.com']
4
      def parse(self, response):
6         for title in response.css('.post-header>h2'):
              yield {'title': title.css('a ::text').get()}
8
          for next_page in response.css('a.next-posts-link'):
10             yield response.follow(next_page, self.parse)
```

Code Listing 2: Python Scrapy Spider Example

3.2.5 MongoDB

*MongoDB*²⁷ is a “document-based [...] database built for modern application developers [...]” (MongoDB, 2020) that is used by companies such as Facebook, Google, Ebay, and Electronic Arts – to name few

²²<https://scrapy.org/>

²³<http://nutch.apache.org/>

²⁴<https://openbixo.org/documentation/getting-started/>

²⁵<http://bit.ly/1dYRV2n>

²⁶<http://code.google.com/p/crawler4j/>

²⁷<https://www.mongodb.com/>

of them. Its main difference to usual Structured Query Language (SQL) databases is the concept of a document-based storage. It is possible to store entire documents in a single table cell where it could contain several data types. Thus, MongoDB “supports arrays and nested objects as values.” (Trelle, 2014, p. 4), so that the structure is comparable to the JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), such as shown in listing 3. In summary, the approach used for this thesis, picked NoSQL, more specifically

```
1 {
2   "_id": "5cf0029caff5056591b0ce7d",
3   "firstname": "Jane",
4   "lastname": "Wu",
5   "address": {
6     "street": "1 Circle Rd",
7     "city": "Los Angeles",
8     "state": "CA",
9     "zip": "90404"
10  },
11  "hobbies": ["surfing", "coding"]
12 }
```

Code Listing 3: MongoDB Example Entry

MongoDB, over typical SQL databases because it is free, easy to use and optimized for modern applications. Evaluations show, that NoSQL databases performed very well in different tests (Gandini, Gribaudo, Knottenbelt, Osman, & Piazzolla, 2014, p. 14). However, it has to be mentioned that “there is no evaluation available which answers the question ‘which tool is the right tool for the job?’ [...]” (Hecht & Jablonski, 2011, p. 6).

Related to this job, the JSON like structure makes it easy to store the Javascript objects directly into the database without observing a specific model or rules. Moreover, it is very compatible with Scrapy and Python, but the most important reason is the good cooperation with the container framework Docker. Databases such as MySQL or MariaDB are developed and optimized for running on a single server and are able to control and work with a lot of various databases or clients. Since this thesis uses a containerized service structure, each service, the database, should be as tiny as possible to run flawless on the stack. However, MySQL and MariaDB are comparatively huge software packages and not optimized for container applications (Öggl & Kofler, 2018, p. 156).

3.2.6 Docker

*Docker*²⁸ describes itself as a framework to “modernize [...] applications [...]” and “[...] accelerate innovation” (Docker, 2019). Here, the main advantage is the capability to “securely build, share, and run modern applications anywhere” (2019). Therefore, Docker uses so-called containers²⁹ to orga-

²⁸<https://www.docker.com/>

²⁹<https://docs.docker.com/get-started/part2/>

nize and orchestrate software products, in which “Containers allow certain software components [...] to run without the overhead of a virtual machine.” (Öggl & Kofler, 2018, p. 9). These containers can be set up and used much faster than typical virtual machines, because on a server only docker must be installed in order to download and start the created images. In terms of security, Bui has found out that “Docker containers are fairly secure, even with the default configuration” (2015). Another reason for choosing Docker is the fast growth and continuously development, since Red Hat supports Docker in Red Hat Enterprise Linux (Merkel, 2014, p. 5).

Docker Swarm:

Applications can be easily scaled across multiple servers, by using container orchestration in the form of Docker Swarm³⁰. A Docker Swarm is an orchestration³¹ system to control and manage all nodes and the containers that run there. The swarm automatically scales the entire application to use all resources in the best possible way. Furthermore, it uses self-healing; once a node fails, its services are automatically picked up by another node to keep the program alive (Öggl & Kofler, 2018, p. 363). This is possible due to the use of Microservices, that are small applications that can be deployed independently, scaled independently and tested independently (Thönes, 2015). Each of those are doing a small self-contained task, to do justice to the Keep It Simple, Stupid (KISS) principle. Every container that breaks can easily restart and reconnect to the network, while the rest is still working as expected.

For this study the main advantage of using a container structure is the fast and secure way to deploy an application. Once a change has been made to the code, only the following steps need to be followed to update the productive application:

- Build the Image
 - *docker build [OPTIONS] PATH*
- Push the Image to the registry
 - *docker push [OPTIONS] NAME[:TAG]*
- Login to the Docker Swarm Master Node
- Redeploy the application
 - *docker deploy [OPTIONS] STACK*

All services changed will be updated automatically to provide continuous production.

³⁰<https://docs.docker.com/get-started/part4/>

³¹<https://www.docker.com/products/orchestration>

3.2.7 Traefik

With the use of Docker it is very easy to include a reverse proxy server to navigate all incoming requests to the right route. There, such a server can be described as the following:

“A reverse proxy [...] provides access to web-enabled applications from a browser connected to the public network. The reverse proxy rewrites requests and responses so that the browser directs requests to the reverse proxy, from which the requests can be directed to the appropriate server on the public network or the private network.” (Araujo, Best, Heitmueller, & Tikhonov, 2005, p. 1)

This study uses *Traefik*³² which is an “Open-Source reverse proxy and load balancer for HTTP and TCP-based applications that is easy, dynamic, automatic, fast, full-featured, production proven, provides metrics, and integrates with every major cluster technology” (Traefik, 2019), as it is described on the website. Using such a technology makes it possible to make the application accessible only via certain ports, e.g. 80 or 443. Services that use other ports to the outside can be addressed via sub domains, e.g. *api.elaisa.org* for *elaisa.org:8080*. To clarify the benefits of Traefik and to make it more comprehensible, one may take a look at the following Figure 6.

Figure 6: Traefik - Overview
Source: (Traefik, 2019)

³²<https://traefik.io/>

3.3 Conceptualizing a language-based Search Engine

Using the software packages shown, the implementation of the application can now be planned and visualized, for which this chapter intends to outline the process thereof. The following models aim to show the architecture on which the application will base on, including container structure, web crawler construction, database modeling, interface definition, and the role of the above-named software packages.

3.3.1 Architecture

First, the application's architecture has to be explained to understand the entire context. With respect to this interplay of different services it can be said that it generally uses the Model/View/Controller (MVC) design pattern (Krasner, Pope, et al., 1988). Thus, there is a model represented by the database, a UI to show the content as view and an API as controller to send data to the front-end and manipulate the model.

As mentioned before in section 3.2.6, all services are wrapped in Docker stacks, which provide local networks to let the software parts communicate with each other securely (see Figure 7). On the one hand, the *Elaisa* stack organizes the entire application that is shown as the search engine in the browser. On the other hand, the *Monitoring* stack helps the administrator to observe the current status and behavior of the server and thus to be able to correct errors in good time – for this study the *Monitoring* stack only is included to exactly correct those server errors. If one looks at Figure

Figure 7: Architecture - Docker

7 from left to right in detail, the application is accessible through the ports 80, for the Hypertext

Transfer Protocol (HTTP), and 443 for HTTPS to make it possible to use a Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate. This certificate is necessary for securing the Internet's web traffic; first introduced by Netscape in 1995 to provide confidentiality, integrity, and identity to network communications (Hickman & Elgamal, 1995). This way, a user can be sure that the input of, for example, login information will be sent securely.

Which service can now be achieved is controlled by the reverse proxy server used (see section 3.2.7). Using such a proxy is a common process in the development of Docker web applications. All accesses are forwarded centrally to the ports provided, with sub domains of the global host name being used for all services (Öggl & Kofler, 2018, p. 136). In this way, the following URLs can be reached via the Internet:

- api.elaisa.org
- elaisa.org
- grafana.elaisa.org
- alertmanager.elaisa.org

This group is called 'Exposed Services' as none of the other groups and its services can be accessed from the public network. The first one exposes a RESTful HTTP-based API that allows complete control over the search engine. It is used by the second exposed service – the UI. It serves the entire website that is usually the main tool users see and utilize, while the next two URLs won't be visited by non-administrators. Because they are located in the *Monitoring* stack, they're exposed to observe the behavior of the server running the web application, such as mentioned before. Apart from this brief insight and the related documentation³³, this stack won't be discussed further because it is not important for the main task of this work.

Next, there is a NoSQL database representing the global storage used by the services: API, Crawler and DB. By virtue of different networks none of the other services is able to reach and manipulate the database. All in all, there are three different networks, each with its own specific scope: Frontend, Database and Monitoring. As mentioned in the previous sentence, the database network allows to reach the service DB. To exchange data through the networks, services like API are connected with both networks, Frontend and Database. Thus, the API is able to send the requested data to the UI. The User Interface is located in the Frontend network to cleanly separate it from the backend logic.

3.3.2 Crawling, Indexing, and Ranking

Such as mentioned before, the web crawler is an important part as it is responsible for filling the database with informative data. Therefore, it combines the tasks of crawling websites, indexing the

³³<https://github.com/dasmemeteam/language-level-search-engine/tree/master/monitoring>

content and ranking the stored documents.

The following part will describe how the developed crawler works. For that, Figure 8 tries to summarize the whole service Crawler (see Figure 7). In the center there is the main actor, the crawler. It interacts with several products to store the extracted and analyzed data into the database. Starting on the right side of the Figure, the crawler doesn't monitor the whole WWW but a defined list of allowed domains. Due to the fact that this search engine aims to help people learning a new language, it only allows domains of news websites, such as The Guardian or BBC. This means that the database only contains news sites building the knowledge basis of this search engine, hence the crawler is defined as a topical or better focused crawler, since it is specified on news and therefore restricted to a certain section of the WWW (Chakrabarti, Van den Berg, & Dom, 1999). Another reason why such a list of allowed domains is used is the huge number of not suitable websites comprising just advertising or adult content. Related to the allowed domains, the list of start URLs is filled with some example articles picked from the news sites to give the crawler a point to start its job, such as shown in Figure 1. To make Figure 8 easier to understand, the entire thing can be imagined as a loop which repeats

Figure 8: Elaisa Web Crawler - Overview

itself until there are no foreign URLs left. So every time a new website is visited, the crawler extracts the content, such as meta data, text and links, and sends it to the categorizer. The categorizer then calculates the language level for the given text based on some Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithms and techniques. General speaking, the CEFR vocabulary lists from section 3.1 are used to calculate the percentage of a word that occurs in a certain language level and in the current text. If the majority of the words contained in the text are assigned to level B2, the probability increases that the entire text is also categorized with B2. However, it must be noted that the higher a word is classified, the less often it has to appear in a text in order to influence the overall level. This is because higher classified words can often be more difficult to learn. After categorizing the extracted text, the new level-meta-data are returned to the crawler which then adds this information to the existing extraction. Finally, a pipeline is started to automatically update the database, in detail the inverted index and basis of crawled websites – more in section 3.3.3.

Pipeline:

In detail, the pipeline consists of four parts:

1. Ignore duplicates
2. Store extracted data into database
3. Calculate the page rank and update database document
4. Add the Document's Identifier (ID) and new words to the inverted index

As described before, storing duplicates is a main problem of a crawler, since the database would use more storage than needed; therefore every document should be unique. Before the crawler is able to calculate the page's rank given the included links, those links and the rest of the extracted data has to be stored first.

Afterward the rank pipeline part uses all available documents in the database and updates or defines a new ranking value for each item. In order to do so, the ranking method used adds the *PageRank* and *TF/IDF* from section 2.2. Finally this value is stored as the website's *pagerank*. These two ranking methods are sufficient to specify a clear position in the result set for each record and at the same time to qualitatively evaluate the referenced content.

Right after that, the inverted index is updated to append the current document ID to all words that occur in the related website and, if necessary, add new words to the index. Thus, it notes how often, at what position and in which exact documents the current word appears. With this information, that is extracted based on the theory in section 2.3, it is then possible to return all records for the searched term.

3.3.3 Database

Such as the Figures 7 and 8 show, the database is used globally for accessing all kind of data. While the crawler continuously fills it with the latest websites, the API uses the database to get results the user requested via the UI.

Figure 9 shows a model of the used MongoDB database, consisting of four so-called collections containing documents. Collections make no demands on the documents they contain, so that no special data type has to be specified (Trelle, 2014, p. 25-26). However, to make it clear at this point, the data types used are shown in the Figure. The two main collections are *news_en_EN* and *inverted_index_en_EN*, where each of them represents three different collections for the different languages the search engine pays attention on (English, German, Spanish). These collections are basically needed for the search engine. The other two are used to manage the user's profile and store the login data or search history – why the application uses a profile functionality is described in section 4.3. As mentioned before in section 3.2.5 there are no rules to store information into a document, thus there are several levels of key-value pairs. Moreover, the private key is generated automatically and represented as a bold written *_id* at the beginning of each document. As may be noticed, the *word* key is also displayed in bold. MongoDB provides a so-called index³⁴ functionality to improve the database's query performance where the documentation says that “if an appropriate index exists for a query, MongoDB can use the index to limit the number of documents it must inspect” (MongoDB, 2019). As the API uses the *word* key to get all result documents, the index needs to be set for a faster query. Starting with *news_en_EN*, each document stores the entire extracted data of one website the crawler returned. Beside standard HTML data like the *url*, *title* or other meta tags, the most important values are *level*, *level_meta*, and the *pagerank* value. Without them it wouldn't be possible to provide searching for different language levels – the main feature of this work. How the pagerank is calculated is explained in section 2.2. The *level* and *level_meta* values are used later in the API to filter the database regarding to the user's choice of a language level and then to visualize them in the UI's results view.

Diving into the collection *inverted_index_en_EN*, it is shown that it stores the ID from *news_en_EN* for each document in a list. With this relation the API later is able to return the content stored for each website to the UI to create a typical search engine result page (more in section 3.3.6). Furthermore, the API can make use of the advantages of using an inverted index because every word in the index contains the relation for all documents the word appears in. To now get the frequency of each word used for calculating the rank of the related website, the index stores the position of the word in the related website. So the system can count how often a word appears in a document by just adding all equivalent IDs to a final sum. Nothing more is necessary to benefit from an inverted index.

Without going into too much detail about the user profile feature, the *user* collection stores all registered persons. Thus, personal information such as the first name, last name or email address

³⁴<https://docs.mongodb.com/manual/indexes/>

Figure 9: MongoDB Database Model

are stored in there. To log in as a user, the email is used together with a password, which is stored encrypted as a binary string. To make use of an account in this search engine, there is a *search_history* collection as well. Every document in it stores information about a search, a logged in user performed in the past. Because of that, it stores the user's email address, whereby the address represents a relation with the *user* collection. Next to the email it contains the searched level, language, (search) query, and the date when it was searched.

3.3.4 Application Programming Interface

In the previous sections the abbreviation API has been called several times because it plays a main role in the entire application. Generally, it can be considered as a global connector and data postman. To describe what's exactly meant by that, the words of Joshua Bloch can be used:

“An Application Programming Interface specifies a component in terms of its operations, their inputs, and outputs. Its main purpose is to define a set of functionalities that are independent of their implementation, allowing the implementation to vary without compromising the users of the component.” (Bloch, 2014)

This overview clarifies that API is just a term describing various different interface functions. In this application, it is used to connect the UI and the backend. This interface offers the user the possibility to ask the database for specific information, such as result documents. Figure 10 shows an overview of the used API. But, before diving into the individual endpoints, the used paradigm has to be explained. As can be seen in the Figure, the endpoints use *GET* or *POST* prefixes, which are two of a total of eight verbs defined in the current version of HTTP. These ones here are defined as Representational State Transfer (REST) operations, where *GET* is the most general and important one. According to the specifications, it is used to retrieve information that is detected by the Uniform Resource Identifier (URI). The returned information then is represented by a specific entity displayed in an standardized form (Tilkov, Eigenbrodt, Schreier, & Wolf, 2015, p. 53). In this work, the chosen form for presenting the result is JSON (Bray, 2014). Next to Comma-Separated Values (CSV) (Shafranovich, 2005) and the Extensible Markup Language (XML) (Thompson, 2014), it is one of the main data exchange notations. The reason why this choice was made is the origin in JavaScript while the web application's UI also uses this programming language (see sections 3.2.1 and 3.3.6).

First, the interface can be separated into two main parts, where the first one is inescapable for a search engine:

- Search
- User

The Search endpoints provide the functionality to find documents and, furthermore, get all words of the inverted index. If a user now types in a search value, a chosen language, and a language level, all

Figure 10: Elaisa API - Overview

this information is sent to the */find* endpoint which in turn queries the database using the given filter. In Figure 11 one may will notice that there are three other parameters this endpoint needs: *loggedIn*, *email*, and *key*. As mentioned before in section 3.3.3, the user has the choice to log in to an account to

Find Documents	
GET	/find
	query
	level
	language
	loggedIn
	email
	exclude (optional)
	mode (optional)
	key

Figure 11: Elaisa API - Find Documents

store the search history. Therefore, the API needs to know if the user is currently logged in because it would then store the search event into the *user* database collection. Beyond, the API is secured with a key so that only authorized persons can access the interface's functionality (Farrell, 2009). Using such a key as required parameter is one of the three common authentication methods:

- HTTP Basic Authentication
 - Uses a **username** and **password** to provide a user's authentication.

- API Keys
 - Uses a **unique generated value** to provide a fast and easy authentication.
- OAuth
 - This approach lets the user log into a system, whereby this system first return a **token** that is needed to finally log into the target. It is fundamentally a much more secure way than the other methods.

For this work, the API Key mechanism seems to be the best choice since other developers shall be able to query the API in the future without creating an user account or using complex authentication processes. The following example defines the parameters of a random user's search to demonstrate what was described before:

- Query: UK
- Level: B2
- Language: English
- LoggedIn: false
- Email: *default*
- Key: *API Key*

Section 3.3.1 already stated the used domains for the web application where the first one, *api.elaisa.org*, is used to call this interface. Thus, the collected data shown above are concatenated to the following GET request:

- GET `api.elaisa.org/find?query=UK&level=B2&language=en&loggedin=false&email=default&key=API-Key`

Going back to Figure 11, there are two more optional parameters *exclude* and *mode*. Excluding is used to query only a part of the available information for a primary resource (Tilkov et al., 2015, p. 39), so that it is provided to remove either the *wikipedia* or the *documents* object from the result to prevent unnecessary data exchange. *Mode* filters every *item* object included in *documents* to minimize the object for the client's needs, too. Here, the client can choose between *compact*, *analysis* or keep it empty. The first mode removes the *text* and *links* information, while the second one only hands back the *_id*, *url*, *level*, *level_meta*, and *pagerank*. The example listing 4 shows a basic response template to clarify the described features. To give back a standardized JSON response, the entire schema is returned. So the client can verify, for example, if the endpoint returned a spell check by reading the value of *result.spellcheck.checked*. If it is true, the client knows that there are no results in the other

```

1 {
2   "result": {
3     "spellcheck": {
4       "checked": false,
5       "correctquery": ""
6     },
7     "wikipedia": {
8       "url": "",
9       "title": "",
10      "summary": ""
11    },
12    "documents": {
13      "length": 0,
14      "items": [
15        {
16          "_id": "",
17          "url": "",
18          "meta": {
19            "language": "",
20            "keywords": "",
21            "author": "",
22            "publisher": "",
23            "desc": "",
24            "date": ""
25          },
26          "title": "",
27          "abstract": "",
28          "text": "",
29          "level": "A1",
30          "level_meta": {
31            "difficulty": "hard",
32            "A1": 0,
33            "A2": 0,
34            "B1": 0,
35            "B2": 0,
36            "C1": 0,
37            "C2": 0,
38            "unknown": 0
39          },
40          "links": [],
41          "pagerank": 0
42        }
43      ]
44    }
45  }
46 }

```

Code Listing 4: API /find Endpoint response

two objects, since if a user sent a misspelled word, the API only returns the most probable right one.

The other stated endpoints */getwords* and */gettopics* on the one hand return all words and on the other hand return n random chosen topics that are stored in the inverted index. The first response is used by the UI to generate the auto-complete feature in the search bar (see Figure 17). As soon as a user types in a search value, the auto-completion tries to suggest a matching value which is stored in the database. Because of that, the user automatically recognizes what he or she can best search for. The */gettopics* endpoint though is used to provide a topic-search feature where the user is able to click on a suggested term to search for documents instead of defining a specific query. Thus, the person can first look around and observe all possible results. Since both endpoints just return simple information without manipulating the database, they are the only ones that doesn't require an API key. Diving into the User part of the application interface, all these endpoints are utilized to make the profiles' views available. Whenever a user wants to sign in (see Figure 21), the top left endpoint (*/signin*) is called. This endpoint compares the given *username* and *password* with data stored in the database. If a user isn't registered yet, he or she fills out a form where the Sign Up button calls the */signup* endpoint that creates a new account if the user isn't already registered. Since the profile's main feature is the personal monitoring of a user's search history, the */searchhistory* endpoint is called whenever a user visits the profile page. Last but not least the two endpoints shown at the bottom of Figure 10 change the password, where the */forgotpassword* endpoint sends a link to change the password via mail.

At long last these seven API endpoints are used on different parts of the web application. The latest and always updated documentation can be found here:

- <https://api.elaisa.org>

3.3.5 Natural Language Understanding / Processing

The service API not only queries the database and acts as a postman, as described in the previous section. A more interesting functionality is that the API examines the search query for speech errors. By using NLP and Natural Language Understanding (NLU) the incoming information is analyzed in order to help the user finding the best results. The techniques that are used in this process, are referred to as named entity extraction and lemmatization. Before the used techniques can be explained, NLP and NLU needs to be defined:

“Natural Language Processing is a theoretically motivated range of computational techniques for analyzing and representing naturally occurring texts at one or more levels of linguistic analysis for the purpose of achieving human-like language processing for a range of tasks or applications.” (Liddy, 2001)

Accordingly, it handles the processing of natural language but it does not understand the user's intent. This part is handled by NLU whose term originated in the early days of Artificial Intelligence (AI),

whereby a full working NLU system would be able to “translate the text into another language” or “answer questions about the content of the text” (Liddy, 2001). Often these two techniques are merged into one since NLU still remains the goal of NLP (Liddy, 2001).

Now the above mentioned NLP tasks can be explained in detail. Checking the search query’s spelling has become the standard in recent years as 10-15% of search queries contain spelling mistakes (Cucerzan & Brill, 2004). Therefore such analysis can provide useful suggestions for up to 70% of the errors (Levene, 2011, p. 105). Like in Google Search, this work shows additional evidence for spelling suggestions in the results for a given query (Chen, Li, & Zhou, 2007). If a user wants to search for the term ‘summer’ but accidentally typed ‘sammer’, the system will suggest to start another search with the most probable correction – in this case ‘summer’.

Another approach this work uses is to lemmatize the search query. This procedure is necessary since the user could search for something like ‘dogs’ in which the inverted index only stores the term ‘dog’. Without lemmatizing and therefore removing the plural ‘s’, the search engine wouldn’t return documents containing the word ‘dog’.

Last, the user has the ability to search for named entities, such as ‘Angela Merkel’, ‘United Kingdom’ or ‘Apple’. Those terms, often compounds, represent entities which might appear in a huge number of indexed documents. In this way, the user can ask the search engine for articles about the company Apple or the German chancellor Angela Merkel and will receive all documents talking about these topics.

3.3.6 Structure of the User Interface

By now, all the necessary components of the web application have been addressed. Next, the proposed features and their accessibility on the website can be discussed.

As mentioned in section 3.2.1, the User Interface is developed with React and thus rendered in the browser as a single-page-application. With respect to Web 2.0, websites have to fit into various sizes for desktop or mobile use and beyond provide an experience that is more like a desktop application than a simple static website showing some information (O’reilly, 2007). Exactly this is what this work’s web application should be – intuitive and dynamic. This desktop-like appearance is caused by real time data fetching without reloading the page as only the application’s state controls which component is rendered at which time – the user is not aware of this. Therefore, it is very straight forward to create a responsive mobile view, as well. The UI simply decides if a component needs to be rendered on a specific device or not, and thanks to modern Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) and Material-UI, the chosen components can be modified for the current size easily. What this responsive design looks like is shown and described in section 4.4.

Figure 12 shows a general overview of the UI’s structure. The user opens *www.elaisa.org* on his or her web browser and directly lands on the Main page consisting of the search bar and a few other

components. From this point on, the user has several options to navigate through the application. If he

Figure 12: Structure of the User Interface - Overview

or she types in a search query and starts the process of finding results, the application navigates him or her to the Result page. There he or she has the possibility to either visit one of the result websites, start a new search or navigate back to the Main page. If the user wants to sign up or sign in, he or she can click on an avatar shown on the Main page that will navigate him or her to the Sign In site. Now he or she can log into his or her already existing account or register for a new one by clicking on a button that navigates him or her to the Sign Up view. As soon as the user is logged in, the Account and Profile pages are available. Due to a navigation bar, one is always able to navigate through all the pages, besides Result – it has to be searched for something to visit the Result page. As can be seen on the left of Figure 12, there is a Bookmarks page connected to the Results group and the general website. The Bookmarks page, as the name indicates, shows all bookmarked articles the user may want to read in the future. Therefore, one marks an article in the results list to make it visible in the list of bookmarks; it is only possible to mark articles on the Result page. Since all required information are stored in the browser-window's local storage, there is no need to create a new account in Elaisa to mark some articles. Thus, this feature provides an easy way to lay away various articles without thinking about user data.

3.4 Evaluation

The following evaluation is intended to numerically record the development by means of various tests. Accordingly, three tests will evaluate the search engine for the following criteria:

1. Classification of the language level of a website by a trained teacher

2. Measurement of Recall and Precision for search results

3. Usability Test for evaluating the User Interface

For the first test, three websites are classified by a trained English teacher. Thus, the calculated language level of the algorithm can be compared with that of the specialist, so that direct suggestions for improvement can be worked out. A test is of great use here, as the categorizer in interaction with the web crawler reflects the main part of the search engine. However, since this work is not focused on the development of the categorizer, the results of the teacher can be considered and implemented in future developments. The second test concentrates on the measurement of two functions: Recall and Precision. The two values are used to calculate the relevance of returned results in a search engine, since relevance is “the attribute or criterion reflecting the effectiveness of exchange of information between people (i.e., users) and IR systems in communication contracts” (Saracevic, 1999, p. 1059). In other words, the result has to match my search query and satisfy my need for information – the result has to be relevant to me as a person. For this reason, paying attention on relevance is one of the key concepts of information science (Borlund, 2003). Finally, a group of usability test users will appraise the developed search engine in respect to user experience, handling, and design to find out if the User Interface is designed in a user-friendly and easy to understand way.

3.4.1 Classification of the language level of a website by a trained teacher

Beginning with the professional classification by a trained teacher, the voluntary should be introduced: Anke Grünspek studied English and Spanish at the RWTH Aachen, the University of Cologne, and the Universidad de Granada and has been teaching both subjects at the Berufskolleg Kleve of the district of Kleve since 2001, mainly in courses leading to the general and technical college entrance qualification. Since 2017 she has been the head of the English and Spanish department at the Centre for Practical Teacher Training in Duisburg - Seminar Berufskolleg. She trains teachers in both subjects for the Berufskolleg and regularly supervises internship semester students in both technical and interdisciplinary support.

3.4.2 Measurement of Recall and Precision for search results

As mentioned before, these two values are used to represent the level of satisfaction for a specific search; but for the sake of the user, it is more important that at least some search results are produced. This means, the database, especially the inverted index, has to be filled with a representative quantity of documents and words to return the most wanted response – if the database doesn't contain the right documents regarding the users' needs, the quality of the ranking doesn't matter.

To calculate these ones in section 4.6.2, Recall and Precision have to be defined. Back in the year 1955, Kent, Berry, Luehrs, and Perry first talked about the evaluation of an Information Retrieval

system whereupon the following two formulas arose later:

$$Precision = \frac{foundRelevantDocuments}{foundRelevantDocuments + notRelevantFoundDocuments}$$

$$Recall = \frac{foundRelevantDocuments}{foundRelevantDocuments + relevantNotFoundDocuments}$$

(Stock & Stock, 2013, p. 113-114).

Related to Information Retrieval evaluation methods, these two formulas only represent one part. One could evaluate the engine's *Similarity* or *Indexing Quality* (Depth, Effectivity, Consistency) as well (Stock & Stock, 2013, p. 115-116; Stock & Stock, 2013, p. 817-824).

3.4.3 Usability Test for evaluating the User Interface

Finally, a usability test helps to identify alleged errors in use. This is necessary, since the results found must be presented in a clear and informative way. A typical user has to be able to control the search engine without reading a list of instructions about difficult commands and complicated search techniques. Ultimately, this web application is developed for the average user, who can directly express his or her opinion and evaluation by means of the test. This person is represented by a randomly selected group of 17 people of different ages. Before diving into the test itself, the term 'usability' has to be defined:

“Usability deals with the ability of a person to perform certain tasks or achieve larger goals with a product [...]” (Reiss, 2015, p. 15)

This means, “the user can do what he or she wants to do the way he or she expects to be able to do it, without hindrance, hesitation, or questions” (Rubin & Chisnell, 2008, p. 4). Thus, it could be the case, that the UI needs to be changed regarding the testers' opinions and suggestions. To test each person equally, a so-called usability test is used, where the tester is asked to complete several tasks. The chosen test for this work is shown in the appendix. In Summary, those tests are basically used to make design decisions or to eliminate frustration for users (Rubin & Chisnell, 2008, p. 21).

Talking about the test itself it can be stated, that it uses a kind of Heuristic evaluation (Nielsen, 1994, p. 413), since each participant acts as a specialist who judges whether an element is easy and understandably usable. To develop the catalog of questions, two fellow students performed a pretest. The final one contains 20 tasks, with the first three dealing with the basic Main page. The next ten ask the tester to search for documents and evaluate the features of the Result page (see Figure 12). Finally, another seven are based on the profile feature, whereby the tester has to create an account, visit the Profile pages, change his or her password, and download data as PDF file. These questions

were developed on the basis of testing all the different functions of the search engine. With this set all necessary improvements can be recorded.

In order to measure the execution, the number of clicks the user needs to complete each task is counted. This enables the evaluation to find out whether certain features are difficult to find or aren't described adequately. For this reason, he or she also has to use the Think-Aloud method to verbalize what he or she is doing while going through the test. This method is very helpful, since "thinking aloud can [...] help participants think through the design problem and form ideas for recovering. While this isn't always what they would do in real life, their doing so will come up with ideas about how to remedy design problems" (Rubin & Chisnell, 2008, p. 54). An alternative would be to record a video of the participants and the device's screen to analyze it afterward (Lewis, 1982, p. 1). However, in this case, people's suggestions for improvement are more important than a detailed view of usage behavior. As a recorder and observer (Veldof, 2003, p. 133-134), the author notes down all spoken comments that could then be implemented at a later stage. Furthermore, he interacts with the participant to let him or her suggest improvements. Accordingly, the number of clicks help getting a numerical value of the tester's usage, while the noted comments make it possible to compare the clicks with the actual thoughts.

4 Results: Presentation of the Web Application

This chapter aims to present the web application, database, evaluation, and the final implementation of all the features and services presented in the last chapters.

4.1 Overview

Figure 13 shows the first page a user sees after visiting elaisa.org. There he or she is able to control

Figure 13: Elaisa.org - Main Page

the whole search engine, while the main feature is positioned in the center of the screen; the search functionality. Here, the user has to define the **result language**, **language level**, and **search term** to find specific documents for the current need of information. Extends to this, the user has the opportunity to directly search for different topics to get an overview about available documents or just to get familiar with the provided functionalities. Next to the possibility to change the UI's language or read the legal notices, there is a menu on the top left and a profile section on the top right.

4.1.1 Menu

From anywhere in the web application the user can open the menu (see Figure 14) to navigate back to the Main view, take a look on the stored bookmarks, take a language test, ask for help, look into the source code or report an issue. It may be that the user doesn't know what level to look for because

Figure 14: Elaisa.org - Menu

he or she never used CEFR before (see section 3.1). In this case, he or she can take a test for the desired language, for example English. Furthermore, the user can open a helping pop-up window (see section 4.1.3) if he or she doesn't know how to use this search engine at all. Even if most of the participants of the usability test (see section 3.4.3) did very well, there could be difficulties for some users – for example non digital natives. The other options **View Source** and **Report Issue** are aimed at technophile persons or developers who want to help improving Elaisa.

4.1.2 Bookmarks Page

As described in section 4.2, it is possible to add an article to the applications' bookmarks. As soon as the user wants to observe these stored articles, the Bookmarks page can be opened in the menu. After clicking on **Bookmarks** (see Figure 14), the application changes to the view shown in Figure 15. Now, all bookmarks can be found in sorted tabs. One can filter by one of the three provided languages

Figure 15: Elaisa.org - Bookmarks Page

or by the used CEFR language levels. Thus, the user is able to create a list of interesting articles he or she wants to read in the future. A workload can also be stored, which should be processed. So it is possible to save heavier articles before the new state of knowledge. At long last, every bookmark presents all necessary information of the referenced website, such as the language analysis or a button to visit the page. Of course, it is also feasible to delete every bookmark from the list.

4.1.3 Asking for Help

Such as mentioned before, besides finding out which language level the user has, he or she may need an introduction to the main features Elaisa provides. For this reason, an information window (see Figure 16) can be opened from the menu. If that doesn't help either, a detailed description can be opened by clicking on **MORE INFOS**. This description will then adapt in the future with the published renewal in order to ensure that anyone interested can easily access the functions of this search engine.

Figure 16: Elaisa.org - Asking for Help

4.2 Searching for Articles

If the user is familiar with the engines' basics, using the example from the previous sections, it is now possible to define the search for the term "football" in Figure 13. While defining the search, Elaisa helps the user to get the best result by suggesting (see section 3.3.4) what he or she might type in the text field, as shown in Figure 17. Paying attention to these suggestions prevents an empty result set, since the search engine only suggests words that are also present in the inverted index (see section 4.5.2), so that each selected term appears in at least one result document. After selecting **English** as

Figure 17: Elaisa.org - Auto-Completion

result language, **All** as language level, **football** as search term, and finally clicking on the search icon, the web application changes the view to the Result page to present all found documents to the user, as shown in Figure 18. Such as in the previous example (see section 3.4.2), the search engine returned five documents in total, in which the Wikipedia article for "football" is displayed as well. If the user now clicks on **LEARN MORE**, in the Wikipedia preview, the application navigates him or her to the Wikipedia page. To share this result with another person, one can use the share menu on the bottom right to copy the link or send it via mail. If the search doesn't satisfy the need for information, it can be adjusted in the top bar. There, the user is also able to open the main menu or navigate back to the home view. However, the main section of this view is displayed on the left side of the screen. All found documents are sorted by the calculated rank (see section 2.2) and presented as unique result items. From left to right, each result item consists of the document's level display, a bookmark icon, general information about the article, and the analysis icon (see Figure 19). Therefore, the user has the ability to directly decide whether an article is suitable for reading or not, since he or she can take a look on the total level and, for more detailed information, on the analysis. The analysis includes the total language level, the language level distribution, and the degree of difficulty of word length. The distribution should help to understand the difficulty of the referenced text, as it shows how many percent of words are in which language level. The word length lets the user know if the text contains

elaisa English All

5 results for "football"

C2 [Stoke City sack Nathan Jones with club in Championship relegation zone | Football | The Guardian](#)
<https://www.theguardian.com/football/2019/nov/01/stoke-city-sack-nathan-jones-championship-club-relegation-zone-football>
 Stoke have sacked manager Nathan Jones after enduring their worst start to a season for more than a century
[Stoke City,Championship,Football,Sport](#)

C1 [West Ham director of football Mario Husillos's future in doubt amid slump | Football | The Guardian](#)
<https://www.theguardian.com/football/2019/nov/06/west-ham-director-of-football-mario-husillos-future-doubt-manuel-pellegrini>
 West Ham's alarm at their recent slump has raised doubts over the future of Mario Husillos, the club's director of football and one of Manuel Pellegrini's closest allies
[West Ham United,Football,Sport](#)

C2 [Vitória Guimarães' Bruno Duarte strikes late to deny Arsenal in Europa League | Football | The Guardian](#)
<https://www.theguardian.com/football/2019/nov/06/vitoria-guimaraes-arsenal-europa-league-group-f-match-report>
 Bruno Duarte's stoppage-time scissor-kick made it 1-1 after Shkodran Mustafi's header in Group F of the Europa League
[Europa League,Vitória de Guimarães,Arsenal,Football,Sport](#)

C2 [Red Star Belgrade 0-4 Tottenham: Champions League – as it happened | Football | The Guardian](#)
<https://www.theguardian.com/football/live/2019/nov/06/red-star-belgrade-v-tottenham-hotspur-champions-league-live?page=with:block-5dc32e22810867dceb1d00e7>
 Son Heung-Min scored twice as Spurs quelled the hostile atmosphere in Serbia for a crucial victory in Group B. Scott Murray was watching.
[Champions League,Red Star Belgrade,Tottenham Hotspur,Football,Sport](#)

Wikipedia

Football

Football is a family of team sports that involve, to varying degrees, kicking a ball to score a goal. Unqualified, the word football normally means the form of football that is the most popular where the word is used. Sports commonly called football...

[LEARN MORE](#)

Figure 18: Elaisa.org - Result Page

[Stoke City sack Nathan Jones with club in Championship relegation zone | Football | The Guardian](#)
<https://www.theguardian.com/football/2019/nov/01/stoke-city-sack-nathan-jones-championship-club-relegation-zone-football>
 Stoke have sacked manager Nathan Jones after enduring their worst start to a season for more than a century
[Stoke City,Championship,Football,Sport](#)

C2

Language Level: C2

Language Level distribution:

A1: 45% | A2: 13% | B1: 8% | B2: 4% | C1: 1% | C2: 3% | Unknown: 27%

Word length: Easy

Figure 19: Elaisa.org - Result Item

a lot of long words that could be more difficult. It separates between *Easy* and *Hard*. To the analysis' left, there is an icon to add this specific article to the search engines' bookmarks. This might be helpful if the user wants to read it later or found it interesting (see section 4.1.2). The shown example document is already stored as a bookmark, the icon is filled.

4.2.1 Spelling Suggestion

Of course, it can also happen that a user doesn't follow the suggestions and makes an incorrect entry that returns an empty result. Because of that, section 3.3.5 talks about trying to correct the user's search query if it is misspelled to help the user finding any documents at all. Elaisa uses this technique and presents a button (see Figure 20) showing the proposed correct query which repeats the search as soon as the user clicks it.

Figure 20: Elaisa.org - Spelling Suggestion

4.2.2 Boolean Searches

In most cases, users would certainly search not just for a word, but for a sentence or a collection of words to get a specific result. As already mentioned at the end of section 2.3, an inverted index provides this functionality using boolean search queries. Accordingly, an *and* or *or* can be added to the search in order to either only search for articles in which the intersection of the two terms occurs or in which either one or the other term occurs. Thus, a valid query could look like the following:

- football and summer
- football or summer

4.3 User Profile

As mentioned at the end of section 3.3.3, the user is offered to create a profile that stores the searches while the person is logged in. This functionality should make it possible to observe all searches and to extract a learning curve from this data. In the introduction (see section 1), an example was mentioned in which a person searches for documents over a longer period of time and increases the language level after an indefinite period in order to learn new knowledge. The following section explains how such a profile can be created and used using illustrative examples.

4.3.1 Create Account / Sign In

However, before data can be saved and tracked, an account must be created. Therefore, the user has to click on the profile icon shown on the top right in Figure 13. A menu is opened, the only button called **Sign In** redirects the visitor to the corresponding Sign In page (see Figure 21). If no registration data

Figure 21: Elaisa.org - Sign In Page

is available yet, one can click the **DON'T HAVE AN ACCOUNT? SIGN UP** button to be redirected to the Sign Up page. The *first name*, *last name*, *email address*, and *password* must then be entered there. Before finally clicking the **SIGN UP** button, the user must agree that the search engine may save the search history in the future. As soon as the account has been successfully created, the new user will be informed of this by a green bar in the lower left corner of the screen. Shortly after, he or she will be directed back to the previous window to log in. If he or she has registered using the valid *email address* and the correct *password*, the search engine in turn leads this user back to the Main

page, the profile icon now representing an image of the user. If one clicks on this icon again, which now shows the profile picture, a menu opens with three options: **Profile**, **Account**, **Sign out**.

4.3.2 Profile Page

To view all previous searches, the Profile page (see Figure 12) can be opened by clicking on the **Profile** button. Figure 22 shows a typical user's profile overview. In the case of this user, a total of

Figure 22: Elaisa.org - Profile Page

108 searches were carried out while logged in, all of whom searched for English documents. With 82% share, *All* is the most wanted level for this user. If one takes a look at the table below, it shows that the last search was carried out on January 4, 2020 and looked for documents about football. At the bottom of this page one will see a button called **PDF Download**. If this is clicked, the profile data is downloaded as a PDF file (see Figure 23).

ALEXANDER TEUSZ

5.1.2020, 14:22:02

www.elaisa.org

OVERVIEW

This document gives you an overview about your current search history and the distribution of language levels you searched for.

SEARCH HISTORY

Language Level

- All: 89
- A1: 3
- A2: 0
- B1: 3
- A2: 1
- C1: 1
- A2: 11

Times searched

Language

- Deutsch: 0
- English: 108
- Español: 0

Times searched

Elaisa - Language Level Search Engine - All rights reserved - 2020

Figure 23: Elaisa.org - Profile Data PDF

4.3.3 Account Page

Since it could be the case at some point that the user wants to change his or her password, the Account page can be opened, that is shown in Figure 24. The profile picture and email address are shown there. By entering the old and a new password, this can be changed. If it is the case that the current password

Figure 24: Elaisa.org - Account Page

has been forgotten, a new one can be created by receiving a specific link via mail. Therefore, one has to click on **FORGOT PASSWORD?** on the Sign In page (see Figure 21).

Generating a Profile Picture:

In all previous Figures where the user is logged in, a profile picture of this person is displayed. Since the server environment used doesn't allow the storage of many user images due to the minimal resources, the Gravatar³⁵ service is used as the source of the profile image. Several images and email addresses can be stored there, which may use different services, should one register with an email address that refers to a profile picture that was uploaded to Gravatar.

4.4 Responsive Web Design

Back in 2010, Maurer, Hausen, De Luca, and Hussmann conducted an online survey, which concluded that “more and more people prefer using original content instead of the mobile version [...]” (2010) and that there were “no significant performance increase when comparing both versions – the mobile

³⁵<https://en.gravatar.com/>

and the desktop one [...]” (2010). However, over the past ten years, many new smartphones have been launched that have caused a change in the use of modern websites, such as Enge presents in his article from 2019. Figure 25 is based on 0.9 trillion visits in 2016, 1.0 trillion visits in 2017, and 0.9 trillion web visits in 2018. As can be seen, 58% of all web visits were carried on mobile devices in 2018, whereby it seems to continue that the major traffic will come from mobile devices in the future. Based on this data, one should also consider optimizing this web application for mobile devices.

Figure 25: Desktop vs. Mobile Web Visits (US)
Source: Modified from (Enge, 2019)

Because the participants had to test a desktop and a mobile version, this optimization has already been implemented and improved using the usability test (see section 3.4.3). Before this version can be presented, the term Responsive Web Design needs to be defined:

“Responsive [Web] Design means adapting the layout and content to the respective medium [...]” (Reiss, 2015, p. 56)

So the web application should not only work perfectly on a smartphone but also on a tablet or smart TV. As an example, Figure 26 shows the Main and Result page from the perspective of an iPhone 8 user. On the left view the download button mentioned in the results of section 3.4.3 and the more compact positioning of the components can be seen. The right view shows directly that the Wikipedia article on mobile devices is displayed above the search results and also the bar with which the search can be changed in this case is opened via the magnifying glass icon. To enlarge the text of the Wikipedia article on the small screen, the button to the right of the search term can be clicked. As

Figure 26: Elaisa.org - Mobile Main Page / Mobile Result Page

usual in the Google Android operating system, there is a button in the lower right corner - in this case the share button. At long last, the entire application is designed to be operated using typical hand movements on the smartphone.

4.4.1 Dark Mode

However, this adjustment no longer only involves presenting the content appropriately on the screen and supporting gestures. Since operation systems such as Mac OSX, IOS or Android support the so-called Dark Mode or Dark Theme, more and more applications are adapting to the dark display of the operating system, for example to protect the eyes in dim light. Due to this functionality, Elaisa also adapts to the current settings of the user and, as shown in the Figures 27 and 28, also turns dark if it is desired. Such a dark view shall “reduce the luminance emitted by device screens, while still

Figure 27: Elaisa.org - Main Page - Dark Mode

Figure 28: Elaisa.org - Result Page - Dark Mode

meeting minimum color contrast ratio” (Material Design, 2020). Furthermore Material Design says that they “[.] help improve visual ergonomics by reducing eye strain, adjusting brightness to current lighting conditions, and facilitating screen use in dark environments – all while conserving battery power. Devices with OLED screens benefit from the ability to turn off black pixels at any time of day” (2020).

4.5 Productive Database

This section describes the productive database on the basis of which the evaluations were carried out. An example is shown for all of the four collections used: *news_en_EN*, *inverted_index_en_EN*, *user*, *search_history*.

4.5.1 Crawled Article Entry

Starting with the first collection, a single article that is stored in *news_en_EN* is shown in Figure 29. In addition to the general data extracted from the website, such as the title or text, the lower part of

```
_id: ObjectId("5dc41dc9d4e1042ad56a100a")
url : "https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/jun/17/iran-it-will-break-uranium-stockpile-limit-set-nuclear-deal "
meta : Object
  language : "en "
  keywords : "Iran nuclear deal,Iran's nuclear programme,Iran,US foreign policy,Middle East and North Africa,World news "
  author : "Patrick Wintour "
  publisher : null
  desc : "Atomic agency says limit will be breached on 27 June and Iran could start enriching up to 20% "
  date : null
  title : "Iran to break uranium stockpile limit set by nuclear deal in 10 days | World news | The Guardian "
  abstract : "4 months old "
  : "Atomic agency say limit will be breached on 27 June and Iran could start enriching up to 20 Diplomatic editor Tehran ha sped up the
  level : "C2 "
level_meta : Object
  difficulty : "easy "
  A1 : 41
  A2 : 7
  B1 : 8
  B2 : 8
  C1 : 2
  C2 : 2
  unknown : 32
links : Array
pagerank : 0.00003115264797507789
```

Figure 29: Elaisa.org - Database - Crawled Articles Entry

the entry is of great importance. So this article was given the overall *level C2* and a *pagerank* of approximately 0.000031. The value of the ranking can be said to be in this range for all entries. The list of included links is not shown in this Figure because it is too long.

4.5.2 Inverted Index Entry

Each of these entries that are represented by Figure 29, are referenced in the *inverted_index_en_EN* to make it easier and faster to find them. One can take a look at Figure 30, where the entry for the term ‘football’ is listed. There are seven *documents* that contain this term in total, while three of them are the same. That means, the term occurs three times in this specific article. If one now removes all duplicates, there are only the known five result articles in the list, that were used in the previous examples.

```

    _id: ObjectId("5dc41e1092d0414f666cd060")
    word: "football"
  documents: Array
    0: Object
      id: "5dc41e03d4e1042ad56a1016"
      pos: 103
    1: Object
      id: "5dc41e03d4e1042ad56a1016"
      pos: 247
    2: Object
      id: "5dc41e03d4e1042ad56a1016"
      pos: 13
    3: Object
      id: "5dc41e40d4e1042ad56a101f"
      pos: 105
    4: Object
      id: "5dc41fb1d4e1042ad56a1043"
      pos: 125
    5: Object
      id: "5dc421a3d4e1042ad56a1061"
      pos: 161
    6: Object
      id: "5dc421efd4e1042ad56a1064"
      pos: 161

```

Figure 30: Elaisa.org - Database - Inverted Index Entry

4.5.3 User's Profile Entries

To make use of the user's profile, his or her account needs to be stored as well. Therefore, the *user* collection contains all registered accounts. As one can see in Figure 31, each entry contains the *first*

```

_id: ObjectId("5d5304b8cc0cbb5d44ba7e9f")
firstname: "Alexander"
lastname: "Teusz"
email: "teusz.alexander@gmail.com"
password: Binary( 'JDJiJDE0JG1rR0c30XFWR0UxNmtRL0x4YzRGZS5MZUpLM21MSmZoUDNJTXA5aWdpbHh2UmJBVG5XUFMu' )

```

Figure 31: Elaisa.org - Database - User Entry

name, *last name*, *email address*, and the encrypted *password*. This information can now be used to log in or change the password.

However, in order to be able to access the essential data, namely the saved search queries, the email address is used as a foreign key in the *search_history* collection (see Figure 32). All searches of every user are stored in this collection, while the *email* is used to filter only the needed entries for the current account. All filtered entries together form the content of the table shown in the Figure 22. Using this storage method, it is possible to insert or remove certain entries user-specifically without

```
_id: ObjectId("5e10950a5b0b209098cbed1f")  
email: "teusz.alexander@gmail.com"  
level: "all"  
language: "en"  
query: "football"  
date: "04.01.2020 13:37"
```

Figure 32: Elaisa.org - Database - Search History Entry

problems.

MongoDB (see section 3.2.5) makes it very easy to store and access information from various applications. Also, it is possible to add new fields to each collection without running into issues, if there may will be another, better way of storing Elaisa's data in the future. Accordingly, this technology has proven to be an easy-to-integrate and problem-free solution.

4.6 Results of the Evaluation

Finally, the results of the evaluations are presented, which have contributed significantly to the development of the final web application.

4.6.1 Results: Classification of the language level of a website by a trained teacher

At the time of the professional assessment (see section 3.4.1), the database was filled for a huge part with articles from BBC or The Guardian, whereby Mrs. Grünspek tested the following three items, including the values *Language Level* and *Word Length* calculated by the machine:

- <https://www.theguardian.com/sport/live/2019/oct/02/rugby-world-cup-2019-new-zealand-v-canada-live>
 - Language Level: C2
 - Word Length: Easy
- <https://www.theguardian.com/film/2019/oct/02/its-very-modern-armando-iannucci-rips-up-rules-with-dickens-adaption>
 - Language Level: C1
 - Word Length: Difficult
- <https://www.bbc.com/worklife/article/20191106-the-house-built-by-2-million-instagram-followers>
 - Language Level: C2
 - Word Length: Easy

Such as described in section 3.3.2, the web crawler uses a list of URLs to start its search to provide high-quality results and prevent unnecessary adult or advertising content. However, since this URL list consists of example articles from The Guardian, BBC, Hannahgale, Word of Wonderlust, and The Sun, the average language level seems to be in the area of B2 - C1, as the teacher explains in her evaluation. Furthermore she says, those magazines are part of the well-known Quality Papers which also include The New York Times or Washington Post. Therefore, she suggests to let the web crawler categorize articles from The Daily Mail, for example, which is part of the so-called Tabloid Press. In order to improve the range of articles using the different language levels A1 - B2, Mrs. Grünspek gives the advice to take along newspapers that are produced for English courses, whereat those papers are divided into the categories READ ON (A2 - B1) and Word & Press (B2 - C1).

Talking about the actual evaluation of the machine's categorization, regarding the teacher's assessment, the shown results correspond to reality, right? No, not really. Taking a look at the language analysis of the second article shown in the upper list, it looks such as the following:

- Language Level: C1
- Language Level distribution:
 - A1: 48%
 - A2: 6%
 - B1: 7%
 - B2: 5%
 - C1: 2%
 - C2: 1%
 - Unknown: 31%
- Word length: Hard

Most of the found words in the analyzed text are assigned to A1 and not to the overall level C2. However it should be noted that section 3.3.2 mentioned, the higher a word is classified, the less often it has to appear in a text in order to influence the overall level. Further, 31% of the words couldn't be allocated at all, as the categorizer wasn't able to do that. How these 31% would influence the calculated level isn't clear. As can be seen, the categorizer works fine but definitely needs to be optimized in the future; even if there will probably be a few percent of unassignable words in every text. However, the overall analysis doesn't have to be redone since the search engine provides several articles in different language levels to let the user read specific texts in the searched level.

4.6.2 Results: Measurement of Recall and Precision for search results

In order to fill the variables of the formulas described in section 3.4.2, an example search result has to be given. In this case the response for articles about 'football'. To make this test a bit more generic, it is searched for English articles in all language levels. So if it is now searched for those documents on elaisa.org, a client retrieves five documents in total:

1. Stoke City sack Nathan Jones with club in Championship relegation zone — Football — The Guardian
 - Language Level: C2
 - Website: <https://www.theguardian.com/football/2019/nov/01/stoke-city-sack-nathan-jones-championship-club-relegation-zone-football>
2. West Ham director of football Mario Husillos's future in doubt amid slump — Football — The Guardian
 - Language Level: C1

- Website: <https://www.theguardian.com/football/2019/nov/06/west-ham-director-of-football-mario-husillos-future-doubt-manuel-pellegrini>
3. Vitória Guimarães' Bruno Duarte strikes late to deny Arsenal in Europa League — Football — The Guardian
 - Language Level: C2
 - Website: <https://www.theguardian.com/football/2019/nov/06/vitoria-guimaraes-arsenal-europa-league-group-f-match-report>
 4. Red Star Belgrade 0-4 Tottenham: Champions League – as it happened — Football — The Guardian
 - Language Level: C2
 - Website: <https://www.theguardian.com/football/live/2019/nov/06/red-star-belgrade-v-tottenham-hotspur-champions-league-live?page=with:block-5dc32e228f0867dcebfd00e7>
 5. Red Star Belgrade 0-4 Tottenham: Champions League – as it happened — Football — The Guardian
 - Language Level: C2
 - Website: <https://www.theguardian.com/football/live/2019/nov/06/red-star-belgrade-v-tottenham-hotspur-champions-league-live?page=with:block-5dc316ad8f08be4a102e4411>

For Precision, a user now has to decide which of the shown documents are relevant for the given search. As four of five documents are different from each other and all of them talk about an event in football, the number of relevant documents is four. The last two returned results link to the same website where they differ only in the last part of the URL. Those cases occur because many URLs out there have query parameters for analytics or session information (Matsudaira, 2014, p. 11). Therefore one of them isn't relevant directly. Filling in the variables, the Precision calculates the following value:

$$Precision = \frac{4}{4+1} = 0.8$$

As only one document isn't relevant, the Precision for this one search is 0.8, which is a very high and satisfying result. Here it is important to note that only five results are given; with more returned documents the Precision could decrease. So, in summary, 80% of the shown documents are relevant regarding the defined search. Therefore, this specific search represents an example of a well performed result. However, due to the fact that there are not many crawled documents in the database, other searches will definitely end in a significantly lower Precision value.

In contrast, the Recall formula doesn't use the ballast but the loss of relevant documents that are stored in the database and not returned as results. Therefore, the search engine may conceal relevant

documents. In order to calculate the loss, one has to look directly in the database to see how many documents were found for the term ‘football’. This value could differ from the amount of shown results, since the web crawler executes several processes to, expand the inverted index, while some of the documents could disappear, by mistake. At the time of the test, the database contained seven unique documents for the chosen term, while only six of them are relevant. The loss consequently is two:

$$Recall = \frac{4}{4+2} \approx 0.667$$

Regarding the Recall, 67% of all relevant documents are retrieved from the database. As already stated at the beginning, the number of documents that are stored at this time is not enough to make a significant evaluation of the entire search engine but it helps to get a general overview about the efficiency.

4.6.3 Results: Usability Test for evaluating the User Interface

Regarding Elaisa’s final usability, it is important to know, that all obstacles mentioned by the testers are improved in the final version of the search engine. Thus, the test serves as an improvement during the actual development. For example, there is a Wikipedia feature on the Result page where the user can click on ‘Learn More’ to visit the original Wikipedia article; on mobile this button seemed to be not visible enough so that some users tried to click on the Wikipedia term (e.g. Football) instead of the dedicated button. Accordingly, on mobile there is now the opportunity to click on the term ether to visit the article. However, there was also the case that some testers needed significantly more clicks for a task but didn’t say it was hard to complete. To give one example, one tester always intuitively tried to take a look into the menu first before thinking about the possibilities shown in the UI. Thus, he needed more clicks than other participants.

The test is separated into two groups, Mobile and Desktop users. A total of 17 people completed 20 tasks, each. The minimum number of clicks for those groups are 55 for Mobile and 45 for Desktop for all tasks in total. At the time of the test, more clicks were needed for some tasks on mobile devices. If one takes a look at the first group, seven of ten testers used an Android device, while three tested Elaisa on an iPhone. Figure 33 shows how the individual testers did based on the number of clicks in total. As can be seen directly, there is a wide range between the minimum of 55 and the maximum of 69 clicks. So the mean is 64, a total of nine clicks above the minimum number of clicks that would be needed to solve all of the 20 tasks. Such as mentioned before, some tasks could not be solved trivially and therefore caused more clicks than necessary – for example open the Wikipedia website for the searched term. Figure 34, therefore, represents the number of clicks per task, to get an overview of the different exercises. In order to get more details about the results of this group, these can be found in the appendix.

In addition, according to user feedback, it was initially not easy to understand how to search for

Figure 33: Number of Clicks of Mobile Users

topics, since only an icon on the Main page should indicate the topic search and not a large button with text, as is now the case (see Figure 13). It is interesting that the users didn't need more clicks, but rather looked for a possible button on the website that could trigger this feature. To solve these problems in use, a total of two improvement rounds were installed in this group, in which the UI was adjusted. After the first four testers, some basic styles and descriptions were changed, for example the button to show the language analysis for a result article, which was a fitness center³⁶ icon first and then was changed to a bar chart icon to represent the analysis. Moreover, on mobile devices there is a button located in the bottom bar of the screen that should help the user to download the web application to the device's home screen. On Android devices, the description needed to be improved. The second round of improvements then changed the mentioned Wikipedia component and replaced the icon for the topic feature with the describing button.

Taking a look at the other group, all seven participants passed the test on the same computer with the same operation system (Mac OSX). Since there was one less task for this group, namely to save the web application on the home screen, and the desktop version was even easier to use at this time, the minimum number of clicks is only 45. As Figure 35 shows, it is immediately noticeable that

³⁶<https://material-ui.com/components/material-icons/#material-icons>

Figure 34: Number of Clicks of Mobile Users per Task

the maximum of 71 clicks is significantly above the mean of 55. It can be said that this person is an older gentleman who isn't a digital native due to his age and has to get to know some functions that seem trivial to younger people. Accordingly, the mean value mentioned is ten clicks above the required minimum. In addition to the fact that a total of two participants had general problems in using modern websites, there were no gross errors in the UI that should have been improved. Ultimately, three younger people only needed three to four clicks more than required. The minimum for this group is 47. In order to compare the distribution of clicks per task in this case as well, Figure 36 can be used. The outliers displayed can be compared with the two inexperienced test persons, as it is the case with task 2.5.. There, one of the two people named needed ten clicks instead of two to view the saved bookmarks in the web application. In this case, this was because this person has never used bookmarks before.

Figure 35: Number of Clicks of Desktop Users

Figure 36: Number of Clicks of Desktop Users per Task

5 Discussion: Conclusion and Limitations

At the beginning (see section 1) the task was to develop a working search engine that can be used online by all interested users. Beyond, it should be answered how a modern search engine can be developed, if it is possible to categorize documents by their language level and then how documents can be searched based on this categorization. If one looks at the results and the evaluations associated with them, a functional and usable search engine was developed within this master thesis, with which categorized documents can be searched successfully. However, the example used shows that this web application is by no means fully developed, as it returns five documents for the term ‘football’. If one searches for the same term on Google, after just 0.9 seconds, approximately three billion documents are displayed as the result set. This comparison is such as the story of David and Goliath, but it should show that there is still a lot of potential in this project. Accordingly, as already mentioned, Elaisa should not be a competitor to Google or Bing, but should give interested parties the opportunity to learn a new language using current and real texts. Thus, Elaisa can be positioned in the category of target-group search engines, where this group consists of students and language enthusiasts (see section 1.1). Reading these documents will then help these people to talk about real-life subjects in personal conversations with language friends. It is therefore not of the utmost importance that as many results as possible are displayed, but that descriptive documents can be searched that support the learning of a new language. This is precisely why the web crawler (see section 3.3.2) only deals with news sites. Since news are generally important for everyone in every country in the world, they can easily be incorporated into dialogues.

5.1 Summary

In order to solve the mentioned tasks, this thesis first explained all used technologies and frameworks, such as CEFR and third-party software to give an overview of the individual parts that form this web application. Secondly, the entire application was conceptualized with respect to the architecture and IR techniques like the web crawler, ranking, and inverted index. It also concentrated on modern concepts including a HTTP-REST API (see section 3.3.4) and NoSQL databases (see section 3.3.3). To provide a user-friendly search, section 3.3.5 talked about suggesting correct search terms with the help of NLU and NLP. Furthermore, to bring all components together in one application, section 3.3.6 draw up a UI to describe how a user could interact with Elaisa. Since this user should be satisfied, this thesis concentrated on evaluating the developed search engine as well. Section 3.4 therefore used a professional English teacher, the measurement of Recall and Precision, and a usability test. As it finally turned out, the search engine works as expected, in which losses in performance must be taken into account, since only one server could be used for the entire stack (see section 3.4). In this case, the formulas Recall and Precision were used as examples to visualize how a search engine could be evaluated in terms of IR methods.

Regarding the two research questions, the first one ‘How can a modern and scalable search engine

be developed that provides to find documents that are categorized by language level?’ was answered by section 3.3. With the help of a container-based architecture, the search engine can be scaled up easily without getting in trouble with server administration. The chosen third-party technologies helped to develop a web application that makes it possible to search for documents. Such tools offer research new ways and possibilities to develop a wide variety of IR systems. Many third-party products are provided as Open-Source and further developed by a community of different personalities. Accordingly, the desires and needs of these people are reflected in the final product. Ultimately, the theoretical approaches of the Information Retrieval department can be easily implemented. The usage of CEFR in cooperation with a web crawler answered the second research question: ‘How can documents be categorized and searched based on language level?’. Section 3.3.2 showed how the categorizer works in summary, while the presented database in section 4.5 showed an example. Therefore, every crawled text document (website, article, etc.) is stored in the database, including the specific language level. With this approach, the fields of linguistics and information science can be combined even more intensely. So far, linguistic theories have been used to detect misspellings or phrase suggestions. However, if one uses these theories for the core of a search engine, as was done in this work, completely new possibilities arise for dealing with text documents. There are almost no limits to the linguistic possibilities.

5.2 Limitations

Talking about losses, a more powerful server environment might have resulted in more than about 3,800 indexed words and approximately 4,500 crawled documents.

5.2.1 Web Crawler CPU Usage

The web crawler, as main service of the application, needs a lot of computing power to extract information from the web pages and categorize them. Correspondingly, the shown examples might have returned more than five results. Figure 37 shows the current Central Processing Unit (CPU) usage of

Figure 37: Elaisa.org - Grafana Service Monitoring - CPU Usage By Container (Top 10)

the applications’ containers while it displays a detailed view of the exposed service Grafana which is used to monitor the server and running application (see Figure 7). As you can see, the orange colored line represents the running web crawler service (*elaisa_crawler...*). This line is almost permanently

in the range of the 80% mark. In places it even reaches 90%, in which the average is 84,31%. Just to reduce the node's usage of the CPU, another server should be added to the Docker Swarm.

5.2.2 Missing Languages

Over and above that, Elaisa is currently not providing searches in German or Spanish, as during the time in which the master thesis was being written, no resources could be found for these two languages. The requested cooperation with language institutes, such as the Goethe Institut³⁷ and Instituto Espanol³⁸, did not lead to any helpful results.

5.3 Alternative Approaches

As part of this collaborative development, alternative solutions and technologies could also be used that serve to improve. An example of this can be given directly: Crawling the web and manually create an inverted index which has to fit into modern search techniques is definitely not the most time-saving and effective way to develop a search engine. However, the requirement of the master seminar, on the basis of which the idea for Elaisa was born, was to develop the search engine from scratch. There are a lot of other possible ways of doing so, in which one of them seems to be a very good alternative to the chosen route – Elasticsearch³⁹. In 2010 Shay Banon published the first version of Elasticsearch as Open-Source project. Generally speaking, this new way of developing a search feature is based on Lucene⁴⁰ which is maintained by the Apache Software Foundation⁴¹ (Hopf, 2016). This framework is very suitable for the functionality of a search engine like Elaisa, because:

“Thanks to the Apache Lucene substructure, Elasticsearch is predestined for full-text search. You can search for individual keywords, phrases or incomplete terms within texts. Especially on websites or in applications that provide large amounts of data, full-text search can be an elementary tool for users.” (Hopf, 2016, p. 5)

The shown architecture of the used web crawler shown in Figure 8 therefore could be separated into the categorizer and Elasticsearch. Thus, a large part of the development could concentrate on improving the basic idea of the search engine - making documents easier to find according to the language level.

As part of the performance improvement, another idea could also be considered. In order to take advantage of other, already widespread search engines, Elaisa could be made available as a browser plugin, which, for example, categorizes the first results displayed on Google in real time. This could have the same positive learning effect on the user as if he or she directly searches on *elaisa.org*.

³⁷<https://www.goethe.de/de/index.html>

³⁸<http://www.institutoespanol.info/>

³⁹<https://www.elastic.co/products/elasticsearch>

⁴⁰<https://lucene.apache.org/>

⁴¹<https://apache.org/>

The browser plugin could also be linked to the Elaisa profile in order to display articles marked or searched for on Google in their own profile. In order to do this, the categorizer would have to be able to categorize up to 10 documents in less than a second, because the usability would suffer from a significant delay compared to Google.

5.4 Future Work

Fixing the mentioned limitations lays the foundation for further work in the future. To avoid the hurdle of missing CEFR lists for German and Spanish, language communities should be included in the project. The idea is to use the advantages of shared knowledge to the advantages of Elaisa. For this reason, the entire project will be provided as Open-Source afterward. This concept⁴² should not only help to get the missing resources, but also to develop the search engine itself. Because, as already said, there is a lot of potential in this project that needs more than one developer to be exploited. Moreover, this work mentioned that the categorizer used is not described in detail as it would go beyond the scope. Another reason is that after completing this master thesis, a second one will follow, which will deal with precisely this topic. It will describe in detail how websites or other text documents can be classified according to the CEFR language levels based on their content. Also, modern technologies and approaches are involved in the further development of this main part of the search engine. This thesis here serves as the basis for creating the framework so that NLP and NLU can be fully focused on in the future work.

All of these suggestions for improvement and ideas form the basis of an unlimited development of this project. With every person who shows interest, new things can be built in to achieve the goal of Elaisa: Learn a new language based on current and understandable news.

⁴²<https://opensource.com/>

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Appendix

Usability Evaluation (English)

Welcome to the Usability Evaluation of Elaisa Search. In this test you will do several tasks like searching documents or creating a user account. The number of clicks you need for each of these steps will be the result.

Important:

All tasks can be solved in the actual web application. You don't have to change the URL or something similar.

Furthermore, please think out loud while doing the tasks to let the tester know.

Open:

www.elaisa.org

Tasks Section 1: General

1. Change the website's language.
2. *On Mobile phones*
 - i. Download the web application to your local Home Screen
3. Open the legal notice (Impressum)

Tasks Section 2: Searching for documents

1. Search for **English** documents containing the term *football** in **all** language levels.
2. Get the language analysis of the first result document.
3. Visit a result web page.
4. Visit the wikipedia article of the search term.
5. Change the language level to **C2** and restart the search.
6. Add any article to the bookmarks.
7. Navigate back to the Main page.

8. Use the *Quick Search* feature to search for documents about **Donald Trump**.
9. Copy the search result's link to the clipboard to share it with your friends.
10. Take a look at your bookmarks.

Tasks Section 3: Creating an account

1. Create a new account.
2. Sign In with the new account.
3. Visit the Profile page.
4. Download the Profile page data as PDF.
5. Visit the Account page.
6. Change your password.
7. Logout from your account.

Usability Test (Mobile Phone)

	Operation System	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
▼ 1	Android			55	61
	Android	1.1.		2	2
		1.2.	Not intuitive where the button is in the browser	5	8
		1.3.		1	1
		2.1.		6	6
		2.2.		1	1
		2.3.	Charts button	1	1
		2.4.		1	1
		2.5.		7	8
		2.6.		1	1
		2.7.		1	1
		2.8.		2	2
		2.9.		2	2
		2.10.		2	2
		3.1.		9	9
		3.2.		3	3
		3.3.		2	2
		3.4.		2	2
		3.5.		2	4
		3.6.		3	3
		3.7.		2	2
▼ 2	Android			55	66
	Android	1.1.	First had to look through the entire website	2	2
		1.2.	Say that its the browser menu button	5	7
		1.3.		1	1
		2.1.		6	6
		2.2.	Icon for Analytics is not so intuitive	1	2
		2.3.		1	1

	Operation System	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
		2.4.	The „more“ info seems to be enough	1	5
		2.5.		7	9
		2.6.	On Android people think that they need to use the browser bookmarks	1	2
		2.7.		1	1
		2.8.	Would be better to use a sentence instead of an icon.	2	2
		2.9.		2	3
		2.10.		2	2
		3.1.		9	9
		3.2.		3	3
		3.3.		2	2
		3.4.		2	2
		3.5.		2	2
		3.6.		3	3
		3.7.		2	2
▼ 3	Android			55	60
	Android	1.1.	Typically the language change is in the upper corner left	2	2
		1.2.		5	5
		1.3.	Very nice that it is a pop up	1	1
		2.1.		6	6
		2.2.	A graph icon would be better	1	1
		2.3.		1	1
		2.4.	The more information and bigger font size in the wikipedia article is a very good feature	1	1
		2.5.		7	7
		2.6.		1	1
		2.7.		1	2

	Operation System	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
		2.8.		2	2
		2.9.	Better color to make it more visible. Green or light blue	2	4
		2.10.	Maybe a view so see all bookmarks doesn't matter which level or language. Maybe show that the level tab bar is swipeable	2	2
		3.1.		9	9
		3.2.		3	3
		3.3.		2	4
		3.4.	Should be in the top - the button. Not everyone scrolls down to the bottom of the website.	2	2
		3.5.		2	2
		3.6.	Show password functionality and repeat password.	3	3
		3.7.		2	2
▼ 4	Android			55	61
	Android	1.1.		2	2
		1.2.		5	7
		1.3.		1	1
		2.1.		6	6
		2.2.	Other button for the language analysis. Maybe a book icon or a shortcut for analysis	1	1
		2.3.		1	1
		2.4.	Change color of „Mehr erfahren“. Should be possible to click on the wikipedia term to visit the wiki site.	1	4
		2.5.		7	7

	Operation System	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
		2.6.		1	1
		2.7.		1	1
		2.8.	Should be a text and not an icon	2	3
		2.9.		2	2
		2.10.		2	2
		3.1.		9	9
		3.2.		3	3
		3.3.		2	2
		3.4.	Just „Generate PDF“ is not enough information. Button could be in the top as PDF icon	2	2
		3.5.	„Account“ link would be better placed in main left menu	2	2
		3.6.	Repeat new password must be added as textfield	3	3
		3.7.		2	2
▼ 5	Android			55	69
	Android	1.1.	overlook	2	7
		1.2.		5	8
		1.3.		1	1
		2.1.		6	6
		2.2.	Maybe chat bubble but don't know if this could be a read out function	1	1
		2.3.		1	1
		2.4.	Maybe add a frame to the wikipedia part. „Mehr erfahren“ button should be marked as link and add link to the term	1	4
		2.5.	Maybe add button „change search“ and show the search bar after clicking on it	7	9

	Operation System	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
		2.6.		1	1
		2.7.		1	1
		2.8.	Add „speed search“ as string to icon	2	2
		2.9.		2	2
		2.10.		2	2
		3.1.		9	9
		3.2.		3	3
		3.3.		2	2
		3.4.	Show that you can scroll down. Add color	2	3
		3.5.		2	2
		3.6.	Add another password textfield to verify the new one	3	3
		3.7.		2	2
▼ 6	Android			55	69
	Android	1.1.		2	2
		1.2.	More detailed description on android	5	11
		1.3.		1	1
		2.1.		6	6
		2.2.		1	1
		2.3.		1	1
		2.4.	Add link to wikipedia term. Add better design to „Mehr erfahren“	1	9
		2.5.	Maybe add an icon to show the search bar parameters and change it easier on mobile devices	7	7
		2.6.		1	1
		2.7.		1	1
		2.8.	Add "Speed search" string to icon	2	2

	Operation System	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
		2.9.		2	2
		2.10.		2	2
		3.1.		9	9
		3.2.		3	3
		3.3.		2	2
		3.4.		2	2
		3.5.		2	2
		3.6.	A third text field for verifying the password would be too much	3	3
		3.7.		2	2
▼ 7	IOS			55	67
	IOS	1.1.		2	2
		1.2.		5	5
		1.3.		1	1
		2.1.		6	6
		2.2.		1	1
		2.3.		1	1
		2.4.	Add link to wikipedia term	1	5
		2.5.		7	7
		2.6.		1	3
		2.7.		1	2
		2.8.	Maybe you don't know what this icon means	2	2
		2.9.		2	5
		2.10.		2	2
		3.1.		9	9
		3.2.		3	3
		3.3.		2	2
		3.4.		2	2
		3.5.		2	2
		3.6.		3	3
		3.7.		2	4
▼ 8	IOS			55	67

	Operation System	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
	IOS	1.1.		2	2
		1.2.	She don't know what the share menu is	5	9
		1.3.		1	1
		2.1.		6	6
		2.2.		1	3
		2.3.		1	1
		2.4.	She first read „Mehr erfahren“ and then „more“ and thus she clicked the right button	1	1
		2.5.		7	9
		2.6.		1	1
		2.7.	She did it with the left menu	1	2
		2.8.	It's not trivial since it doesn't show it clearly.	2	2
		2.9.	The position of the button is not usual for IOS users.	2	5
		2.10.		2	2
		3.1.		9	9
		3.2.		3	3
		3.3.		2	2
		3.4.		2	2
		3.5.		2	2
		3.6.	Responsive Design is broken on iPhone6. Add verifying password text field as third one.	3	3
		3.7.		2	2
▼ 9	Android			55	55
	Android	1.1.		2	2

	Operation System	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
		1.2.	Already knew how to download it in the browser without clicking the download button in the UI	5	2
		1.3.		1	1
		2.1.		6	7
		2.2.		1	1
		2.3.		1	1
		2.4.	"Learn More" to "Open Wikipedia Page"	1	3
		2.5.	Add bar before wiki article to change language level and language	7	7
		2.6.		1	1
		2.7.		1	1
		2.8.	Not trivial since the icon isn't standing for „speed search“	2	2
		2.9.	Its not unnecessary that the button is there to copy the link	2	2
		2.10.		2	2
		3.1.		9	9
		3.2.		3	3
		3.3.		2	2
		3.4.	The position at the end is good since you first have to see what you will download with the PDF	2	2
		3.5.		2	2
		3.6.	Adding another verifying textfield would be more work but better for changing the password	3	3
		3.7.		2	2
▼ 10	IOS			55	62

	Operation System	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
	IOS	1.1.		2	2
		1.2.		5	2
		1.3.		1	1
		2.1.		6	6
		2.2.	More importance for the open analysis button. Maybe bigger size. Maybe put it on the left side and change with bookmarks.	1	5
		2.3.		1	1
		2.4.		1	1
		2.5.	Icon next to the menu icon with „search“ to change the parameters of the search	7	8
		2.6.		1	2
		2.7.		1	2
		2.8.	The speed search terms has to be more separated.	2	4
		2.9.		2	2
		2.10.	Maybe connect UI Language with bookmarks and show the bookmarks for the UI language. CHANGE THE ANALYSIS BUTTON IN THE BOOKMARKS	2	2
		3.1.	Send verification mail after signing up.	9	9
		3.2.		3	4
		3.3.	Show scalleton while loading profile data.	2	2
		3.4.		2	2
		3.5.		2	2

	Operation System	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
		3.6.	Show loading spinner as soon as the user hits the „change password“ button. And disable the button then	3	3
		3.7.		2	2

Usability Test (Desktop)

	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
▼ 1			45	55
	1.1.		2	6
	1.2.		0	
	1.3.		1	1
	2.1.		6	6
	2.2.		1	4
	2.3.		1	1
	2.4.		1	2
	2.5.		3	3
	2.6.		1	1
	2.7.		1	3
	2.8.		1	1
	2.9.	Used the browser search field on computer	2	2
	2.10.		2	2
	3.1.		9	9
	3.2.		3	3
	3.3.		2	2
	3.4.		2	2
	3.5.		2	2
	3.6.		3	3
	3.7.		2	2
▼ 2			45	71
	1.1.		2	4
	1.2.		0	
	1.3.		1	4
	2.1.		6	8
	2.2.		1	2
	2.3.		1	1
	2.4.		1	1
	2.5.		3	10
	2.6.		1	1

	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
	2.7.		1	2
	2.8.	Add same desc as on mobile	1	1
	2.9.		2	2
	2.10.	Only knows browser bookmarks	2	10
	3.1.		9	11
	3.2.		3	3
	3.3.		2	2
	3.4.	Just write „PDF“ with the PDF Icon	2	2
	3.5.		2	2
	3.6.		3	3
	3.7.		2	2
	▼ 3		45	63
	1.1.		2	7
	1.2.		0	
	1.3.		1	1
	2.1.		6	9
	2.2.		1	3
	2.3.		1	1
	2.4.		1	3
	2.5.		3	3
	2.6.	Does not know the bookmarks button	1	5
	2.7.		1	1
	2.8.		1	1
	2.9.		2	2
	2.10.		2	2
	3.1.		9	9
	3.2.		3	3
	3.3.		2	2
	3.4.		2	2
	3.5.		2	2
	3.6.		3	3

	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
	3.7.		2	4
▼ 4			45	57
	1.1.		2	8
	1.2.		0	
	1.3.		1	1
	2.1.		6	8
	2.2.		1	1
	2.3.		1	1
	2.4.		1	1
	2.5.		3	5
	2.6.		1	1
	2.7.		1	1
	2.8.		1	3
	2.9.		2	2
	2.10.		2	2
	3.1.		9	9
	3.2.		3	3
	3.3.		2	2
	3.4.		2	2
	3.5.		2	2
	3.6.		3	3
	3.7.		2	2
▼ 5			45	47
	1.1.		2	4
	1.2.		0	
	1.3.		1	1
	2.1.		6	6
	2.2.		1	1
	2.3.		1	1
	2.4.		1	1
	2.5.		3	3
	2.6.		1	1
	2.7.		1	1

	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
	2.8.		1	1
	2.9.		2	2
	2.10.		2	2
	3.1.		9	9
	3.2.		3	3
	3.3.		2	2
	3.4.		2	2
	3.5.		2	2
	3.6.		3	3
	3.7.		2	2
▼ 6			45	49
	1.1.		2	6
	1.2.		0	
	1.3.		1	1
	2.1.		6	6
	2.2.		1	1
	2.3.		1	1
	2.4.		1	1
	2.5.		3	3
	2.6.		1	1
	2.7.		1	1
	2.8.		1	1
	2.9.		2	2
	2.10.		2	2
	3.1.		9	9
	3.2.		3	3
	3.3.		2	2
	3.4.		2	2
	3.5.		2	2
	3.6.		3	3
	3.7.		2	2
▼ 7			45	48
	1.1.		2	2

	Task	Statement	Minimum Clicks	Clicks
	1.2.		0	
	1.3.		1	1
	2.1.		6	6
	2.2.		1	1
	2.3.		1	1
	2.4.		1	1
	2.5.		3	4
	2.6.		1	1
	2.7.		1	1
	2.8.		1	1
	2.9.		2	4
	2.10.	Show „All“ bookmarks for the three languages and then provide the filter with the flag.	2	2
	3.1.		9	9
	3.2.	Add Profile Icon to the Results View	3	3
	3.3.		2	2
	3.4.		2	2
	3.5.		2	2
	3.6.		3	3
	3.7.		2	2